

SUEWS v2017b Manual

Contents

1 SUEWS v2017b

- 2 Recent publications
- 3 Introduction
- 4 SUEWS and UMEP
- 5 Parameterisations and sub-models within SUEWS
 - 5.1 Net all-wave radiation, Q^*
 - 5.2 Anthropogenic heat flux, Q_F
 - 5.3 Storage heat flux, ΔQ_s
 - 5.4 Turbulent heat fluxes, Q_H and Q_E
 - 5.5 Water balance
 - 5.6 Snowmelt
 - 5.7 Convective boundary layer
 - 5.8 Thermal comfort
- 6 Preparing to run the model
 - 6.1 Preparatory reading
 - 6.2 Decide what type of model run you are interested in
 - 6.3 Download the program and example data files
 - 6.4 Run the model for example data
 - 6.5 Preparation of data
 - 6.5.1 Preparation of site characteristics and model parameters
 - 6.5.1.1 Land cover
 - 6.5.1.2 Anthropogenic heat flux (Q_F)
 - 6.5.1.3 Other information
 - 6.5.1.4 Data Entry
 - 6.5.2 Preparation of the RunControl file
 - 6.5.3 Preparation of the Meteorological forcing data
 - 6.5.4 Preparation of the InitialConditions file
 - 6.6 Run the model for your site
 - 6.7 Analyse the output
 - 6.8 Summary of files
- 7 Input files
 - 7.1 RunControl.nml
 - 7.2 SUEWS_SiteInfo.xlsm
 - 7.2.1 SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt
 - 7.2.1.1 Day Light Savings (DLS)
 - 7.2.1.2 Grid Connections (water flow between grids)
 - 7.2.2 SUEWS_NonVeg.txt
 - 7.2.3 SUEWS_Veg.txt
 - 7.2.4 SUEWS_Water.txt
 - 7.2.5 SUEWS_Snow.txt
 - 7.2.6 SUEWS_Soil.txt
 - 7.2.7 SUEWS_Conductance.txt
 - 7.2.8 SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt
 - 7.2.9 SUEWS_Irrigation.txt
 - 7.2.10 SUEWS_Profiles.txt
 - 7.2.11 SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt
 - 7.2.12 SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt
 - 7.2.13 SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt
 - 7.3 Additional ESTM-related files
 - 7.3.1 ESTMinput.nml

- [7.3.2 SSss YYYY ESTM Ts data tt.txt](#)
- [7.4 Initial Conditions file](#)
 - [7.4.1 InitialConditionsSSss YYYY.nml](#)
- [7.5 Meteorological input file](#)
 - [7.5.1 SSss YYYY data tt.txt](#)
- [7.6 CBL input files](#)
 - [7.6.1 CBL initial data.txt](#)
 - [7.6.2 CBL Input.nml](#)
- [7.7 SOLWEIG input files](#)
- [8 Output files](#)
 - [8.1 Error messages: problems.txt](#)
 - [8.2 Error messages: warnings.txt](#)
 - [8.3 Summary of model parameters: SS FileChoices.txt](#)
 - [8.4 Model output files](#)
 - [8.4.1 SSss YYYY TT.txt](#)
 - [8.4.2 SSss YYYY nn TT.nc \(when ncMode=1 in RunControl\)](#)
 - [8.4.3 SSss DailyState.txt](#)
 - [8.4.4 InitialConditionsSSss YYYY.nml](#)
 - [8.4.5 SSss YYYY snow TT.txt](#)
 - [8.4.6 SSss YYYY BL.txt](#)
 - [8.4.7 SOLWEIGpoiOut.txt](#)
 - [8.4.8 SSss YYYY ESTM TT.txt](#)
- [9 Troubleshooting](#)
 - [9.1 How to create a directory?](#)
 - [9.2 How to unzip a file](#)
 - [9.3 A text editor](#)
 - [9.4 Command prompt](#)
 - [9.5 Day of year \[DOY\]](#)
 - [9.6 First things to Check if the program seems to have problems](#)
 - [9.6.1 A pop-up saying “file path not found”](#)
 - [9.6.2 “%sat_vap_press.f temp=0.0000 pressure dectime”](#)
 - [9.6.3 %T changed to fit limits](#)
 - [9.6.4 %Iteration loop stopped for too stable conditions.](#)
 - [9.6.5 “Reference to undefined variable, array element or function result”](#)
 - [9.6.6 Email list](#)
- [10 Acknowledgements](#)
- [11 Notation](#)
- [12 Development, Suggestions and Support](#)
- [13 Version History](#)
 - [13.1 New in SUEWS Version 2017b \(released 1 August 2017\)](#)
 - [13.2 New in SUEWS Version 2017a \(Feb 2017\)](#)
 - [13.3 New in SUEWS Version 2016a \(released 21 June 2016\)](#)
 - [13.4 New in SUEWS Version 2014b \(released 8 October 2014\)](#)
 - [13.5 New in SUEWS Version 2014a.1 \(released 26 February 2014\)](#)
 - [13.6 New in SUEWS Version 2014a \(released 21 February 2014\)](#)
 - [13.7 New in SUEWS Version 2013a](#)
 - [13.8 New in SUEWS Version 2012b](#)
 - [13.9 New in SUEWS Version 2012a](#)
 - [13.10 New in SUEWS Version2011b](#)
- [14 Differences between SUEWS, LUMPS and FRAISE](#)
 - [14.1 FRAISE Flux Ratio – Active Index Surface Exchange](#)
- [15 References](#)

SUEWS v2017b

The current version of SUEWS is v2017b. The software can be downloaded by completing the form [here](#).

Ward HC, L Järvi, T Sun, S Onomura, F Lindberg, F Olofson, A Gabey, CSB Grimmond (2017) SUEWS Manual V2017b, <http://urban-climate.net/umep/SUEWS> Department of Meteorology, University of Reading, Reading, UK

Page | 3

This wiki page (<http://urban-climate.net/umep/SUEWS>) is regularly updated with new developments. For what's new in this version, see [Version History](#).

The **latest formal** release of SUEWS is **v2017b** (released 1 August 2017).

The manual for SUEWS v2017b can be accessed [here](#) and should be referenced as follows:

Ward HC, L Järvi, T Sun, S Onomura, F Lindberg, F Olofson, A Gabey, CSB Grimmond (2017) SUEWS Manual V2017b, <http://urban-climate.net/umep/SUEWS> Department of Meteorology, University of Reading, Reading, UK

To download the latest version of SUEWS please complete the [online form](#).

Please refer to [Ward et al. \(2017\)](#) for further details v2017a:

Ward HC, Yin San Tan, AM Gabey, S Kotthaus, WTJ Morrison, CSB Grimmond Impact of temporal resolution of precipitation forcing data on modelled urban-atmosphere exchanges and surface conditions International Journal of Climatology doi: 10.1002/joc.5200

See other publications in the next section (if you have papers that could be added, please send them through)

Recent publications

- If you have papers to add to this list please let us and others know via the [email list](#)

[Järvi et al. \(2017\)](#) Application and evaluation in cold climates. Implications of warming

Järvi L, S Grimmond, JP McFadden, A Christen, I Strachan, M Taka, L Warsta, M Heimann 2017: Warming effects on the urban hydrology in cold climate regions Scientific Reports 7: 5833 <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-017-05733-y>

[Kokkonen et al. 2017](#) Downscaling climate (rainfall) data to 1 h

Kokkonen T, CSB Grimmond, O Rätty, HC Ward, A Christen, T Oke, S Kotthaus, L Järvi 2017: Sensitivity of Surface Urban Energy and Water Balance Scheme (SUEWS) to downscaling of reanalysis forcing data Urban Climate <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2017.05.001>

[Ward and Grimmond \(2017\)](#) for example applications:

Ward HC, S Grimmond 2017: Using biophysical modelling to assess the impact of various scenarios on summertime urban climate across Greater London Landscape and Urban Planning 165, 142-161, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2017.04.001>

Demuzere et al. 2017 evaluation in Singapore and comparison with other urban land surface models

Page | 4

Demuzere M, S Harshan, L Järvi, M Roth, CSB Grimmond, V Masson, KW Oleson, E Velasco H Wouters 2017: Impact of urban canopy models and external parameters on the modelled urban energy balance QJRM, 143, Issue 704, Part A, 1581-1596 doi:10.1002/qj.3028

Ward et al. (2016) Evaluation of SUEWS model

Ward HC, Kotthaus S, Järvi L and Grimmond CSB (2016) Surface Urban Energy and Water Balance Scheme (SUEWS): Development and evaluation at two UK sites. Urban Climate <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2016.05.001> Ward et al. (2016)

Ao et al. (2016) Evaluation of radiation in Shanghai

Ao XY, CSB Grimmond, DW Liu, ZH Han, P Hu, YD Wang, XR Zhen, JG Tan 2016: Radiation fluxes in a business district of Shanghai JAMC, 55, 2451-2468 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1175/JAMC-D-16-0082.1>

Onomura et al. (2015) Boundary layer modelling

Onomura S, Grimmond CSB, Lindberg F, Holmer B & Thorsson S (2015) Meteorological forcing data for urban outdoor thermal comfort models from a coupled convective boundary layer and surface energy balance scheme Urban Climate, 11, 1-23 doi:10.1016/j.uclim.2014.11.001

Järvi et al. (2014) Snow melt model development

Järvi L, Grimmond CSB, Taka M, Nordbo A, Setälä H & Strachan IB 2014: Development of the Surface Urban Energy and Water balance Scheme (SUEWS) for cold climate cities, Geosci. Model Dev. 7, 1691-1711, doi:10.5194/gmd-7-1691-2014

Other papers

Introduction

Overview of SUEWS

Surface Urban Energy and Water Balance Scheme (SUEWS) (Järvi et al. 2011^[1], Ward et al. 2016^[2]) is able to simulate the urban radiation, energy and water balances using only commonly measured meteorological variables and information about the surface cover. SUEWS utilizes an evaporation-interception approach (Grimmond et al. 1991^[3]), similar to that used in forests, to model evaporation from urban surfaces.

The seven surface types considered in SUEWS

The model uses seven surface types: paved, buildings, evergreen trees/shrubs, deciduous trees/shrubs, grass, bare soil and water. The surface state for each surface type at each time step is calculated from the running water balance of the canopy where the evaporation is calculated from the Penman-Monteith equation. The soil moisture below each surface type (excluding water) is taken into account.

Horizontal movement of water above and below ground level is allowed. The user can specify the model time-step, but 5 min is strongly recommended. The main output file is provided at a resolution of 60 min by default. The model provides the radiation and energy balance components, surface and soil wetness, surface and soil runoff and the drainage for each surface. Timestamps refer to the end of the averaging period.

Model applicability: SUEWS is a neighbourhood-scale or local-scale model.

SUEWS and UMEP

SUEWS can be run as a standalone model but also can be used within UMEP. There are numerous tools included within UMEP to help a user get started. The SUEWS simple within UMEP is a fast way to start using SUEWS.

The version of SUEWS within UMEP is the complete model. Thus all options that are listed in this manual are available to the user. In the UMEP SUEWS simple runs all options are set to values to allow initial exploration of the model behaviour.

The version of SUEWS within UMEP is a more recent release of the model than the independent SUEWS release.

UMEP		Description	
Pre-Processor	Meteorological Data	<u>Prepare Existing Data</u>	Transforms meteorological data into UMEP format
		<u>Download data (WATCH)</u>	Prepare meteorological dataset from <u>WATCH</u>
	Spatial Data	<u>Spatial Data Downloader</u>	Plugin for retrieving geodata from online services suitable for various UMEP related tools
		<u>LCZ Converter</u>	Conversion from Local Climate Zones (LCZs) in the WUDAPT database into SUEWS input data
	Urban land cover	<u>Land Cover Reclassifier</u>	Reclassifies a grid into UMEP format land cover grid. <i>Land surface models</i>
		<u>Land Cover Fraction (Point)</u>	Land cover fractions estimates from a land cover grid based on a specific point in space
		<u>Land Cover Fraction (Grid)</u>	Land cover fractions estimates from a land cover grid based on a polygon grid
	Urban Morphology	<u>Morphometric Calculator (Point)</u>	Morphometric parameters from a DSM based on a specific point in space
		<u>Morphometric Calculator (Grid)</u>	Morphometric parameters estimated from a DSM based on a polygon grid
		<u>Source Area Model (Point)</u>	Source area calculated from a DSM based on a specific point in space.
	<u>SUEWS Prepare</u>	Preprocessing and preparing input data for the SUEWS model	
Processor	Urban Energy Balance	<u>Anthropogenic Heat (Q_F) (LQF)</u>	Spatial variations anthropogenic heat release for urban areas
		<u>GQF</u>	Anthropogenic Heat (Q _F).
		<u>SUEWS (Simple)</u>	Urban Energy and Water Balance.
		<u>SUEWS (Advanced)</u>	Urban Energy and Water Balance.
Post-Processor	Urban Energy Balance	<u>SUEWS analyser</u>	Plugin for plotting and statistical analysis of model results from SUEWS simple and SUEWS advanced
	Benchmark	<u>Benchmark System</u>	For statistical analysis of model results, such as SUEWS

Parameterisations and sub-models within SUEWS

Net all-wave radiation, Q*

There are several options for modelling or using observed radiation components depending on the data available. As a minimum, SUEWS requires incoming shortwave radiation to be provided.

1. Observed net all-wave radiation can be provided as input instead of being calculated by the model.

2. Observed incoming shortwave and incoming longwave components can be provided as input, instead of incoming longwave being calculated by the model.
3. Other data can be provided as input, such as cloud fraction (see options in [RunControl](#)).
4. **NARP** (Net All-wave Radiation Parameterization, Offerle et al. 2003^[4], Loridan et al. 2011^[5]) scheme calculates outgoing shortwave and incoming and outgoing longwave radiation components based on incoming shortwave radiation, temperature, relative humidity and surface characteristics (albedo, emissivity).

Anthropogenic heat flux, Q_F

1. Two simple anthropogenic heat flux sub-models exist within SUEWS:
 - Järvi et al. (2011)^[1] approach, based on heating and cooling degree days and population density (allows distinction between weekdays and weekends).
 - Loridan et al. (2011)^[5] approach, based on a linear piece-wise relation with air temperature.
2. Pre-calculated values can be supplied with the meteorological forcing data, either derived from knowledge of the study site, or obtained from other models, for example:
 - **LUCY** (Allen et al. 2011^[6], Lindberg et al. 2013^[7]). A new version has been now included in UMEP. To distinguish it is referred to as **LOF**
 - **GreaterQF** (Iamarino et al. 2011^[8]). A new version has been now included in UMEP. To distinguish it is referred to as **GQF**

Storage heat flux, ΔQ_s

1. Three sub-models are available to estimate the storage heat flux:
 - **OHM** (Objective Hysteresis Model, Grimmond et al. 1991^[9], Grimmond & Oke 1999a^[10], 2002^[11]). Storage heat flux is calculated using empirically-fitted relations with net all-wave radiation and the rate of change in net all-wave radiation.
 - **AnOHM** (Analytical Objective Hysteresis Model, Sun et al. 2017^[12]). OHM approach using analytically-derived coefficients. (**Not recommended in v2017b**)
 - **ESTM** (Element Surface Temperature Method, Offerle et al. 2005^[13]). Heat transfer through urban facets (roof, wall, road, interior) is calculated from surface temperature measurements and knowledge of material properties. (**Not recommended in v2017b**)
2. Alternatively, 'observed' storage heat flux can be supplied with the meteorological forcing data.

Turbulent heat fluxes, Q_H and Q_E

1. **LUMPS** (Local-scale Urban Meteorological Parameterization Scheme, Grimmond & Oke 2002^[11]) provides a simple means of estimating sensible and latent heat fluxes based on the proportion of vegetation in the study area.
2. **SUEWS** adopts a more biophysical approach to calculate the latent heat flux; the sensible heat flux is then calculated as the residual of the energy balance. The initial estimate of stability is based on the LUMPS calculations of sensible and latent heat flux. Future versions will have alternative sensible heat and storage heat flux options.

Sensible and latent heat fluxes from both LUMPS and SUEWS are provided in the [model output](#). Whether the turbulent heat fluxes are calculated using LUMPS or SUEWS can have a major impact on the results. For SUEWS, an appropriate surface conductance parameterisation is also critical^{[11][2]}. For more details see [Differences between SUEWS, LUMPS and FRAISE](#).

Water balance

The running water balance at each time step is based on the urban water balance model of Grimmond et al. (1986)^[14] and urban evaporation-interception scheme of Grimmond and Oke (1991)^[3].

- Precipitation is a required variable in the meteorological forcing file.
- Irrigation can be modelled^[1] or observed values can be provided if data are available.

- Drainage equations and coefficients to use must be specified in the input files.
- Soil moisture can be calculated by the model (**Use of observed soil moisture is not possible in v2017b**).
- Runoff is permitted:
 - between surface types within each model grid
 - between model grids (**Not implemented in v2017b**)
 - to deep soil
 - to pipes.

Snowmelt

The snowmelt model within SUEWS is described in Järvi et al. (2014)^[15]. Due to changes in the new model version (since v2016a) when compared to the older versions, the snow calculation has slightly changed. The main difference is that previously all surface state could freeze in 1-h time step but now the amount of freezing surface state is calculated similar way as melt water can freeze within the snow pack. Also the snowmelt-related coefficients have slightly changed (see [SUEWS_Snow.txt](#)).

Convective boundary layer

A convective boundary layer (CBL) slab model (Cleugh and Grimmond 2001^[16]) calculates the CBL height, temperature and humidity during daytime (Onomura et al. 2015^[17]).

Thermal comfort

SOLWEIG (Solar and longwave environmental irradiance geometry model, Lindberg et al. 2008^[18], Lindberg and Grimmond 2011^[19]) is a 2D radiation model to estimate mean radiant temperature.

Overview of scales. Source: Onomura et al. (2015) ^[17]

Preparing to run the model

The following is to help with the model setup. Note that there is a version of SUEWS in [UMEP](#) and there are some starting [tutorials](#) for that. The version there is the same (i.e. the executable) as the standalone version so you can swap to that later once you have some familiarity.

Preparatory reading

Read the manual and relevant papers (and references therein):

- Järvi L, Grimmond CSB & Christen A (2011) The Surface Urban Energy and Water Balance Scheme (SUEWS): Evaluation in Los Angeles and Vancouver. *J. Hydrol.* 411, 219-237. [doi:10.1016/j.jhydrol.2011.10.00](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2011.10.00)
- Järvi L, Grimmond CSB, Taka M, Nordbo A, Setälä H & Strachan IB (2014) Development of the Surface Urban Energy and Water balance Scheme (SUEWS) for cold climate cities. *Geosci. Model Dev.* 7, 1691-1711. [doi:10.5194/gmd-7-1691-2014](https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-7-1691-2014)
- Ward HC, Kotthaus S, Järvi L and Grimmond CSB (2016) Surface Urban Energy and Water Balance Scheme (SUEWS): development and evaluation at two UK sites. *Urban Climate* 18, 1-32. [doi:10.1016/j.uclim.2016.05.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2016.05.001)

[See other publications with example applications](#)

Decide what type of model run you are interested in

	Available in this release
<i>LUMPS</i>	Yes – not standalone
<i>SUEWS at a point or for an individual area</i>	Yes
<i>SUEWS for multiple grids or areas</i>	Yes
<i>SUEWS with Boundary Layer (BL)</i>	Yes
<i>SUEWS with snow</i>	Yes
<i>SUEWS with SOLWEIG</i>	No
<i>SUEWS with SOLWEIG and BL</i>	No

Download the program and example data files

Visit the website to receive a link to download the program and example data files. Select the appropriate compiled version of the model to download. For windows there is an installation version which will put the programs and all the files into the appropriate place. There is also a version linked to QGIS: **UMEP**.

Note, as the definition of long double precision varies between computers (e.g. Mac vs Windows) slightly different results may occur in the output files.

Test/example files are given for the London KCL site, 2011 data (denoted Kc11)

In the following SS is the site code (e.g. Kc), ss the grid ID, YYYY the year and tt the time interval.

Filename	Description	Input/output
<i>SSss_data.txt</i>	Meteorological input file (60-min)	Input
<i>SSss_YYYY_data_5.txt</i>	Meteorological input file (5-min)	Input
<i>InitialConditionsSSss_YYYY.nml(+)</i>	Initial conditions file	Input
<i>SUEWS_SiteInfo_SSss.xlsm</i>	Spreadsheet containing all other input information	Input
<i>RunControl.nml</i>	Sets model run options	Input (located in main directory)
<i>SS_Filechoices.txt</i>	Summary of model run options	Output
<i>SSss_YYYY_5.txt</i>	(Optional) 5-min resolution output file	Output
<i>SSss_YYYY_60.txt</i>	60-min resolution output file	Output
<i>SSss_DailyState.txt</i>	Daily state variables (all years in one file)	Output

(+) There is a second file `InitialConditionsSSss_YYYY_EndOfRun.nml` or `InitialConditionsSSss_YYYY+1.nml` in the input directory. At the end of the run, and at the end of each year of the run, these files are written out so that this information could be used to initialize further model runs.

Run the model for example data

Before running the model for your own data it is good to make certain that you can run the test data and get the same results as in the example files provided. It is recommended that you make a copy of the example output files and put them somewhere else so you can compare the results. When you run the program it will write over the supplied files.

To run the model you can use **Command Prompt** (in the directory where the programme is located type the model name) or just double click the executable file.

Please see [Troubleshooting](#) if you have problems running the model.

Preparation of data

This section describes the information required to run SUEWS for your site. The input data can be summarised as follows:

1. Continuous *meteorological forcing data* for the entire period to be modelled. Note you can not have gaps in the meteorological data. If you need help with preparing the data you may want to use some of the tools in [UMEP](#).
2. Knowledge of the *surface and soil conditions immediately before the start of the run* (if these initial conditions are not known, it is usually possible to determine suitable values by running the model and using the output at the end of the run to infer the conditions at the start of the run).
3. The *location of the site* (latitude, longitude, altitude).
4. Information about the *characteristics of the surface*, including land cover, heights of buildings and trees, radiative characteristics (e.g. albedo, emissivity), drainage characteristics, soil characteristics, snow characteristics, phenological characteristics (e.g. seasonal cycle of LAI).
5. Information about *human behaviour*, including energy use and water use (e.g. for irrigation or street cleaning) and snow clearing (if applicable). The anthropogenic energy use and water use may be provided as a time series in the meteorological forcing file if these data are available or modelled based on parameters provided to the model, including population density, hourly and weekly profiles of energy and water use, information about the proportion of properties using irrigation and the type of irrigation (automatic or manual).

It is particularly important to ensure the following input information is appropriate and representative of the site:

- Fractions of different land cover types and (less so) heights of buildings^[2]
- Accurate meteorological forcing data, particularly precipitation and incoming shortwave radiation^[20]
- Initial soil moisture conditions^[21]
- Anthropogenic heat flux parameters, particularly if there are considerable energy emissions from transport, buildings, metabolism, etc^[2]
- External water use (if irrigation or street cleaning occurs)
- Snow clearing (if running the snow option)
- Surface conductance parameterisation^{[1][2]}

SUEWS can be run either for an individual area or for multiple areas. There is no requirement for the areas to be of any particular shape but here we refer to them as model 'grids'.

Preparation of site characteristics and model parameters

The area to be modelled is described by a set of characteristics that are specified in the [SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt](#) file. Each row corresponds to one model grid for one year (i.e. running a single grid over three years would require three rows; running two grids over two years would require four rows). Characteristics are often selected by a code for a particular set of conditions. For example, a specific soil type (links to [SUEWS_Soil.txt](#)) or characteristics of deciduous trees in a particular region (links to [SUEWS_Veg.txt](#)). The intent is to build a library of characteristics for different types of urban areas. The codes are specified by the user, must be integer values and must be unique within the first column of each input file, otherwise the model will return an error. (Note in [SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt](#) the first column is labelled 'Grid' and can contain repeat values for different years.) See [Input files](#) for details. Note [UMEP](#) maybe helpful for components of this.

Land cover

For each grid, the land cover must be classified using the following surface types:

<i>Classification</i>	Surface type	File where characteristics are specified
<i>Non-vegetated</i>	Paved surfaces	SUEWS_NonVeg.txt
	Building surfaces	SUEWS_NonVeg.txt
	Bare soil surfaces	SUEWS_NonVeg.txt
<i>Vegetation</i>	Evergreen trees and shrubs	SUEWS_Veg.txt
	Deciduous trees and shrubs	SUEWS_Veg.txt
	Grass	SUEWS_Veg.txt
<i>Water</i>	Water	SUEWS_Water.txt
<i>Snow</i>	Snow	SUEWS_Snow.txt

The surface cover fractions (i.e. proportion of the grid taken up by each surface) must be specified in [SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt](#). The surface cover fractions are **critical**, so make certain that the different surface cover fractions are appropriate for your site.

For some locations, land cover information may be already available (e.g. from various remote sensing resources). If not, websites like Bing Maps and Google Maps allow you to see aerial images of your site and can be used to estimate the relative proportion of each land cover type. If detailed spatial datasets are available, [UMEP](#) allows for a direct link to a GIS environment using QGIS.

Anthropogenic heat flux (Q_F)

You can either model Q_F within SUEWS or provide it as an input.

- To model it population density is needed as an input for LUMPS and SUEWS to calculate Q_F .
- If you have no information about the population of the site we recommend that you use the LUCY model^{[6] [7]} to estimate the anthropogenic heat flux which can then be provided as input SUEWS along with the meteorological forcing data. The LUCY model can be downloaded from [here](#).

Alternatively, you can use the updated version of LUCY called [LQF](#), which is included in [UMEP](#).

Other information

The surface cover fractions and population density can have a major impact on the model output. However, it is important to consider the suitability of all parameters for your site. Using inappropriate parameters may result in the model returning an error or, worse, generating output that is simply not representative of your site. Please read the section on [Input files](#). Recommended or reasonable ranges of values are suggested for some parameters, along with important considerations for how to select appropriate values for your site.

Data Entry

To create the series of input text files describing the characteristics of your site, there are three options:

1. Data can be entered directly into the input text files. The example (.txt) files provide a template to create your own files which can be edited with a [text editor](#) directly.
2. Data can be entered into the spreadsheet **SUEWS_SiteInfo.xlsm** and the input text files generated by running the macro.
3. Use [UMEP](#).

To run the xlsm macro: Enter the data for your site into the xlsm spreadsheet **SUEWS_SiteInfo.xlsm** and then use the macro to create the text files which will appear the same directory.

If there is a problem

- Make sure none of the text files to be generated are open.
- It is recommended to close the spreadsheet before running the actual model code.

Note that in all txt files:

- The first two rows are headers. The first row is the column number; the second row is the column name.
- The names and order of the columns should not be altered from the templates, as these are checked by the model and errors will be returned if particular columns cannot be found.
- Since v2017a it is no longer necessary for the meteorological forcing data to have two rows with -9 in column 1 as their last two rows.
- “!” indicates a comment, so any text following “!” on the same line will not be read by the model.
- If data are unavailable or not required, enter the value -999 in the correct place in the input file.
- Ensure the units are correct for all input information. See [Input files](#) for a description of parameters.

In addition to these text files, the following files are also needed to run the model.

Preparation of the RunControl file

In the RunControl.nml file the site name (SS_) and directories for the model input and output are given. This means **before running** the model (even the with the example datasets) you must either

1. open the RunControl.nml file and edit the input and output file paths and the site name (with a [text editor](#)) so that they are correct for your setup, or
2. create the directories specified in the RunControl.nml file

From the given site identification the model identifies the input files and generates the output files. For example if you specify

```
FileOutputPath = "C:\FolderName\SUEWSOutput\" and use site code SS the model creates an output file
C:\FolderName\SUEWSOutput\SSss_YYYY_TT.txt (remember to add the last backslash in windows and slash in Linux/Mac).
```

If the file paths are not correct the program will return an error when run (see [error messages](#)) and write the error to the problems.txt file.

Preparation of the Meteorological forcing data

The model time-step is specified in [RunControl.nml](#) (5 min is highly recommended). If meteorological forcing data are not available at this resolution, SUEWS has the option to downscale (e.g. hourly) data to the time-step required. See details about the [meteorological forcing data](#) to learn more about choices of data input. Each grid can have its own meteorological forcing file, or a single file can be used for all grids. The forcing data should be representative of the local-scale, i.e. collected (or derived) above the height of the roughness elements (buildings and trees).

Preparation of the InitialConditions file

Information about the surface state and meteorological conditions just before the start of the run are provided in the Initial Conditions file. At the very start of the run, each grid can have its own Initial Conditions file, or a single file can be used for all grids. For details see [InitialConditions](#).

Run the model for your site

To run the model you can use **Command Prompt** (in the directory where the programme is located type the model name) or just double click the executable file.

Please see [Troubleshooting](#) if you have problems running the model.

Analyse the output

It is a good idea to perform initial checks that the model output looks reasonable.

<i>Characteristic</i>	Things to check
<i>Leaf area index</i>	Does the phenology look appropriate (i.e. what does the seasonal cycle of leaf area index (LAI) look like?) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Are the leaves on the trees at approximately the right time of the year?
<i>Kdown</i>	Is the timing of the diurnal cycle correct for the incoming solar radiation? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Although Kdown is a required input, it is also included in the output file. It is a good idea to check that the timing of Kdown in the output file is appropriate, as problems can indicate errors with the timestamp, incorrect time settings or problems with the disaggregation. In particular, make sure the sign of the longitude is specified correctly in SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt. Checking solar angles (zenith and azimuth) can also be a useful check that the timing is correct.
<i>Albedo</i>	Is the bulk albedo correct? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> This is critical because a small error has an impact on all the fluxes (energy and hydrology). If you have measurements of outgoing shortwave radiation compare these with the modelled values. How do the values compare to literature values for your area?

Summary of files

The table below lists the files required to run SUEWS and the output files produced. SS is the two-letter code (specified in RunControl) representing the site name, ss is the grid identification (integer values between 0 and 2,147,483,647 (largest 4-byte integer)) and YYYY is the year. TT is the resolution of the input/output file and tt is the model time-step.

The last column indicates whether the files are needed/produced once per run (1/run), or once per day (1/day), for each year (1/year) or for each grid (1/grid).

[B] indicates files used with the CBL part of SUEWS (BLUEWS) and therefore are only needed/produced if this option is selected
 [E] indicates files associated with ESTM storage heat flux models and therefore are only needed/produced if this option is selected

Program	Filename	Description	Location	Option
	<i>SUEWS_V2017b.exe</i>	SUEWS executable	Directory where the program will run	
	<u>Input files</u>			
	<i>RunControl.nml</i>	Specifies options for the model run	Same directory as executable	1/run
	<i>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</i>	Main input file for this site	Input directory	1/run
	<i>SUEWS_NonVeg.txt</i>	Inputs for non-vegetated surfaces	Input directory	1/run
	<i>SUEWS_Veg.txt</i>	Inputs for vegetated surfaces	Input directory	1/run
	<i>SUEWS_Water.txt</i>	Inputs for water surfaces	Input directory	1/run
	<i>SUEWS_Snow.txt</i>	Inputs for snow	Input directory	1/run
	<i>SUEWS_Soil.txt</i>	Inputs for sub-surface soil	Input directory	1/run
	<i>SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt</i>	Inputs for anthropogenic heat flux	Input directory	1/run
	<i>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</i>	Inputs for irrigation	Input directory	1/run
	<i>SUEWS_Profiles.txt</i>	Inputs for hourly profiles (energy use, water use, snow-clearing)	Input directory	1/run
	<i>SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt</i>	Inputs describing within-grid water distribution	Input directory	1/run
	<i>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</i>	Inputs for OHM coefficients	Input directory	1/run
	<i>SUEWS_Conductance.txt</i>	Inputs for surface conductance	Input directory	1/run
	<i>SUEWS_SiteInfo.xlsm</i>	(Optional) spreadsheet for creating input files	Anywhere, but the input files created must be in the input directory	-
	<i>SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt / SSss_YYYY_data_TT.txt</i>	Meteorological input file at model time-step (tt) / lower resolution (TT)	Input directory	1/grid/year or 1/year
	<i>InitialConditionsSSss_YYYY.nml</i>	Initial conditions file	Input directory	1/grid/run or 1/run
	<i>ESTMinput.nml</i>	Specifies options and inputs for ESTM model	Input directory	1/run [E]
	<i>SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt</i>	Inputs for ESTM coefficients	Input directory	1/run [E]
	<i>SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt</i>	Surface temperature data input file at model time-step (tt) / lower resolution (TT)	Input directory	1/grid/year or 1/year [E]
	<i>CBLinput.nml</i>	Specifies options and inputs for CBL model	Input directory	1/run [B]
	<i>CBL_initial_data.txt</i>	Initial data for CBL model	Input directory	1/day [B]
	<u>Output files</u>			
	<i>SSss_YYYY_tt.txt</i>	Model output at model time-step (optional)	Output directory	1/grid/year
	<i>SSss_YYYY_TT.txt</i>	Model output at resolution specified by ResolutionFilesOut	Output directory	1/grid/year
	<i>SSss_DailyState.txt</i>	Status at a daily time step	Output directory	1/grid
	<i>InitialConditionsSSss_YYYY+1.nml</i>	New InitialConditions file written for each grid at the end of each year for multi-year runs. If the run finishes before the end of the year the InitialConditions file is still	Input directory	1/grid/year

	written and the file name is appended with '_EndofRun'		
<i>SS_FileChoices.txt</i>	Summary of model run options	Output directory	1/run
<i>SS_YYYY_TT_OutputFormat.txt</i>	Describes header, units and formatting of the main output file	Output directory	1/run
<i>SSss_YYYY_ESTM_tt.txt</i>	Model output at model time-step (optional)	Output directory	1/grid/year [E]
<i>SSss_YYYY_ESTM_TT.txt</i>	Model output at resolution specified by ResoluionFilesOut	Output directory	1/grid/year [E]
<i>problems.txt</i>	Contains details of serious errors encountered in the model run	Same directory as executable	1/run
<i>warnings.txt</i>	List of potential issues encountered in the model run	Same directory as executable	1/run
<i>CBL_id.txt</i>	CBL model output file for day of year id	Output directory	1/day [B]

Input files

SUEWS allows you to input a large number of parameters to describe the characteristics of your site. You should not assume that the example values provided in files or in the tables below are appropriate. Values marked with 'MD' are examples of recommended values (see the suggested references to help decide how appropriate these are for your site/model domain); values marked with 'MU' need to be set (i.e. changed from the example) for your site/model domain.

RunControl.nml

The file **RunControl.nml** is a namelist that specifies the options for the model run. It must be located in the same directory as the executable file.

The format should be:

```

&RunControl
Parameters and variables (see table below)
/
    
```

In *Linux* and *Mac*, please add an empty line after the end slash.

- The file is not case-sensitive.
- The parameters and variables can appear in any order.

<i>Name</i>	Required /Optional	Description
Model run options		
<i>CBLuse</i>	R	Determines whether a CBL slab model is used to calculate temperature and humidity.
	Value	Comments
	0	CBL model not used. SUEWS and LUMPS use temperature and humidity provided in the meteorological forcing file.
	1	CBL model is used to calculate temperature and humidity used in SUEWS and LUMPS.
<i>SnowUse</i>	R	Determines whether the snow part of the model runs.
	Value	Comments
	0	Snow calculations are not performed.

SOLWEIGUse

*NetRadiationMethod
(previously
NetRadiationChoice)*

*AnthropHeatMethod
(previously
AnthropHeatChoice)*

	1	Snow calculations are performed.
R	Determines whether a high resolution radiation model to calculate mean radiant temperature should be used (SOLWEIG). NOTE: this option will considerably slow down the model since SOLWEIG is a 2D model.	
	Value	Comments
	0	SOLWEIG calculations are not performed.
	1	SOLWEIG calculations are performed. A grid of mean radiant temperature (Tmrt) is calculated based on high resolution digital surface models.
R	Determines method for calculation of radiation fluxes.	
	Value	Comments
	0	Uses observed values of Q* supplied in meteorological forcing file.
	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Q* modelled with L↓ observations supplied in meteorological forcing file. ▪ Zenith angle not accounted for in albedo calculation.
	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Q* modelled with L↓ modelled using cloud cover fraction supplied in meteorological forcing file (Loridan et al. 2011^[5]). ▪ Zenith angle not accounted for in albedo calculation.
	3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Q* modelled with L↓ modelled using air temperature and relative humidity supplied in meteorological forcing file (Loridan et al. 2011^[5]). ▪ Zenith angle not accounted for in albedo calculation.
	100	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Q* modelled with L↓ observations supplied in meteorological forcing file. ▪ Zenith angle accounted for in albedo calculation. ▪ SSss_YYYY_NARPOut.txt file produced. ▪ Not recommended in this release
	200	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Q* modelled with L↓ modelled using cloud cover fraction supplied in meteorological forcing file (Loridan et al. 2011^[5]). ▪ Zenith angle accounted for in albedo calculation. ▪ SSss_YYYY_NARPOut.txt file produced. ▪ Not recommended in this release
300	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Q* modelled with L↓ modelled using air temperature and relative humidity supplied in meteorological forcing file (Loridan et al. 2011^[5]). ▪ Zenith angle accounted for in albedo calculation. ▪ SSss_YYYY_NARPOut.txt file produced. ▪ Not recommended in this release 	
R	Determines method for QF calculation.	
	Value	Comments
	0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Uses values provided in the meteorological forcing file (SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt). ▪ If you do not want to include QF to the calculation of surface energy balance, you should set values in the meteorological forcing file to zero to prevent calculation of QF. ▪ <u>UMEP</u> provides two methods to calculate QF <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <u>LQF</u> which is simpler 2. <u>GQF</u> which is more complete but requires more data inputs
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Currently not recommended! ▪ Calculated according to Loridan et al. (2011)^[5] using coefficients specified in SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt. 	

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Modelled values will be used even if QF is provided in the meteorological forcing file.
	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recommended Calculated according to Järvi et al. (2011)^[11] using coefficients specified in SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt and diurnal patterns specified in SUEWS_Profiles.txt. Modelled values will be used even if QF is provided in the meteorological forcing file.
<i>AnthropCO2Method</i>	R	Determines method for CO2 calculation.
	Value	Comments
	1	Not used.
	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Under development - not recommended in v2017b Calculate CO2 emissions from traffic based on QF calculation.
	3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Under development - not recommended in v2017b Calculate CO2 emissions from traffic from input data provided.
<i>StorageHeatMethod (previously QSChoice)</i>	R	Determines method for calculating storage heat flux ΔQS.
	Value	Comments
	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ΔQS modelled using the objective hysteresis model (OHM)^{[9][10][11]} using parameters specified for each surface type.
	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Uses observed values of ΔQS supplied in meteorological forcing file.
	3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ΔQS modelled using AnOHM. Not available in v2017b
	4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ΔQS modelled using the Element Surface Temperature Method (ESTM) (Offerle et al. 2005^[13]). Not recommended in v2017b
<i>OHMIncQF</i>	R	Determines whether the storage heat flux calculation uses Q* or (Q*+QF).
	Value	Comments
	0	Δ QS modelled Q* only.
	1	Δ QS modelled using Q*+QF.
<i>StabilityMethod</i>	R	Defines which atmospheric stability functions are used.
	Value	Comments
	0	Not used.
	1	Not used.
	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recommended Momentum - unstable: Dyer (1974)^[22] modified by Högstrom (1988)^[23]; stable: Van Ulden and Holtslag (1985)^[24] Heat - Dyer (1974)^[22] modified by Högstrom (1988)^[23]
	3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Momentum: Campbell and Norman (Eq 7.27, Pg97) ^[25] Heat - unstable: Campbell and Norman^[25]; stable: Dyer (1974)^[22] modified by Högstrom (1988)^[23]
	4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Momentum: Businger et al. (1971)^[26] modified by Högstrom (1988)^[23] Heat: Businger et al. (1971)^[26] modified by Högstrom (1988)^[23]
<i>RoughLenHeatMethod (previously RoughLen_heat)</i>	R	Determines method for calculating roughness length for heat.
	Value	Comments
	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Uses value of 0.1z0m.
	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recommended Calculated according to Kawai et al. (2009)^[27].
	3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Calculated according to Voogt and Grimmond (2000)^[28].
	4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Calculated according to Kanda et al. (2007)^[29].
<i>RoughLenMomMethod (previously z0_method)</i>	R	Determines how aerodynamic roughness length (z0m) and zero displacement height (zdm) are calculated.

SMDMethod (previously SMD_Choice)

Value	Comments
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Values specified in <u>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</u> are used. Note that <u>UMEP</u> provides tools to calculate these]. See <u>Kent et al. (2017a)</u> for recommendations on methods. Kent et al. (2017b) have developed a method to include vegetation which is also available within UMEP. Kent CW, CSB Grimmond, J Barlow, D Gatey, S Kotthaus, F Lindberg, CH Halios 2017a: Evaluation of urban local-scale aerodynamic parameters: implications for the vertical profile of wind and source areas <i>Boundary Layer Meteorology</i> 164,183–213 doi: 10.1007/s10546-017-0248-z Kent CW, S Grimmond, D Gatey 2017b: Aerodynamic roughness parameters in cities: inclusion of vegetation <i>Journal of Wind Engineering & Industrial Aerodynamics</i> http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jweia.2017.07.016
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> z0m and zd are calculated using 'rule of thumb' (Grimmond and Oke 1999^[30]) using mean building and tree height specified in <u>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</u>. z0m and zd are adjusted with time to account for seasonal variation in porosity of deciduous trees.
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> z0m and zd are calculated based on the MacDonald et al. (1998)^[31] method using mean building and tree heights, plan area fraction and frontal areal index specified in <u>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</u>. z0m and zd are adjusted with time to account for seasonal variation in porosity of deciduous trees.

R **Determines method for calculating soil moisture deficit (SMD).**

Value	Comments
0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recommended SMD modelled using parameters specified in <u>SUEWS_Soil.txt</u>.
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not currently implemented - do not use! Observed SM provided in the meteorological forcing file is used. Data are provided as <i>volumetric</i> soil moisture content. Metadata must be provided in <u>SUEWS_Soil.txt</u>.
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not currently implemented - do not use! Observed SM provided in the meteorological forcing file is used. Data are provided as <i>gravimetric</i> soil moisture content. Metadata must be provided in <u>SUEWS_Soil.txt</u>.

WaterUseMethod (previously WUChoice)

Value	Comments
0	External water use modelled using parameters specified in <u>SUEWS_Irrigation.txt</u> .
1	Observations of external water use provided in the meteorological forcing file are used.

File-related options

*FileChoice
FileInputPath
FileOutputPath
MultipleMetFiles*

R	Two-letter site identification code (e.g. He, Sc, Kc).
R	Input directory.
R	Output directory.
R	Specifies whether one single meteorological forcing file is used for all grids or a separate met file is provided for each grid.
Value	Comments
0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Single meteorological forcing file used for all grids. No grid number should appear in the file name.
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Separate meteorological forcing files used for each grid. The grid number should appear in the file name.

<i>MultipleInitFiles</i>	R	Specifies whether one single initial conditions file is used for all grids at the start of the run or a separate initial conditions file is provided for each grid.	
		Value	Comments
		0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Single initial conditions file used for all grids. ▪ No grid number should appear in the file name.
		1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Separate initial conditions files used for each grid. ▪ The grid number should appear in the file name.
<i>MultipleESTMFiles</i>	O	Specifies whether one single ESTM forcing file is used for all grids or a separate file is provided for each grid.	
		Value	Comments
		0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Single ESTM forcing file used for all grids. ▪ No grid number should appear in the file name.
		1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Separate ESTM forcing files used for each grid. ▪ The grid number should appear in the file name.
<i>KeepTstepFilesIn</i>	O	Specifies whether input meteorological forcing files at the resolution of the model time step should be saved.	
		Value	Comments
		0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Meteorological forcing files at model time step are not written out. This is the default option ▪ Recommended to reduce processing time and save disk space as (e.g. 5-min) files can be large.
		1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Meteorological forcing files at model time step are written out.
<i>KeepTstepFilesOut</i>	O	Specifies whether output meteorological forcing files at the resolution of the model time step should be saved.	
		Value	Comments
		0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Output files at model time are not saved. This is the default option. ▪ Recommended to save disk space as (e.g. 5-min) files can be large.
		1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Output files at model time step are written out.
<i>WriteOutOption</i>	O	Specifies which variables are written in the output files.	
		Value	Comments
		0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ All (except snow-related) output variables written. This is the default option.
		1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ All (including snow-related) output variables written.
<i>SuppressWarnings</i>	O	Controls whether the warnings.txt file is written or not.	
		Value	Comments
		0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The warnings.txt file is written. This is the default option.
		1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ No warnings.txt file is written. May be useful for large model runs as this file can grow large.
Time-related options			
<i>Tstep</i>	R	Specifies the model time step [s]. A value of 300 s (5 min) is strongly recommended. The time step cannot be less than 1 min or greater than 10 min, and must be a whole number of minutes that divide into an hour (i.e. options are 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 10 min or 60, 120, 180, 240, 300, 360, 600 s).	
<i>ResolutionFilesIn</i>	R	Specifies the resolution of the input files [s] which SUEWS will disaggregate to the model time step. 1800 s for 30 min or 3600 s for 60 min are recommended. (N.B. if ResolutionFilesIn is not provided, SUEWS assumes ResolutionFilesIn = Tstep.)	
<i>ResolutionFilesInESTM</i>	O	Specifies the resolution of the ESTM input files [s] which SUEWS will disaggregate to the model time step.	

<i>ResolutionFilesOut</i>	R	Specifies the resolution of the output files [s]. 1800 s for 30 min or 3600 s for 60 min are recommended.								
<i>DisaggMethod</i>	O	<p>Specifies how meteorological variables in the input file (except rain and snow) are disaggregated to the model time step. Wind direction is not currently downscaled so non -999 values will cause an error.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Value</th> <th>Comments</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Linear downscaling of averages for all variables, additional zenith check is used for Kdown. This is the default option.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Linear downscaling of instantaneous values for all variables, additional zenith check is used for Kdown.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>WFDEI setting: average Kdown (with additional zenith check); instantaneous for Tair, RH, pres and U. (N.B. WFDEI actually provides Q not RH)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Value	Comments	1	Linear downscaling of averages for all variables, additional zenith check is used for Kdown. This is the default option.	2	Linear downscaling of instantaneous values for all variables, additional zenith check is used for Kdown.	3	WFDEI setting: average Kdown (with additional zenith check); instantaneous for Tair, RH, pres and U. (N.B. WFDEI actually provides Q not RH)
Value	Comments									
1	Linear downscaling of averages for all variables, additional zenith check is used for Kdown. This is the default option.									
2	Linear downscaling of instantaneous values for all variables, additional zenith check is used for Kdown.									
3	WFDEI setting: average Kdown (with additional zenith check); instantaneous for Tair, RH, pres and U. (N.B. WFDEI actually provides Q not RH)									
<i>KdownZen</i>	O	<p>Can be used to switch off zenith checking in Kdown disaggregation. Note that the zenith calculation requires location information obtained from SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt. If a single met file is used for all grids, the zenith is calculated for the first grid and the disaggregated data is then applied for all grids.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Value</th> <th>Comments</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No zenith angle check is applied.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Disaggregated Kdown is set to zero when zenith angle exceeds 90 degrees (i.e. sun below horizon) and redistributed over the day. This is the default option.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Value	Comments	0	No zenith angle check is applied.	1	Disaggregated Kdown is set to zero when zenith angle exceeds 90 degrees (i.e. sun below horizon) and redistributed over the day. This is the default option.		
Value	Comments									
0	No zenith angle check is applied.									
1	Disaggregated Kdown is set to zero when zenith angle exceeds 90 degrees (i.e. sun below horizon) and redistributed over the day. This is the default option.									
<i>RainDisaggMethod</i>	O	<p>Specifies how rain in the meteorological forcing file are disaggregated to the model time step. If present in the original met forcing file, snow is currently disaggregated in the same way as rainfall.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Value</th> <th>Comments</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>100</td> <td>Rainfall is evenly distributed among all subintervals in a rainy interval. This is the default option.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>101</td> <td>Rainfall is evenly distributed among among RainAmongN subintervals in a rainy interval – also requires RainAmongN to be set.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>102</td> <td>Rainfall is evenly distributed among among RainAmongN subintervals in a rainy interval for different intensity bins – also requires MultRainAmongN and MultRainAmongNUpperI to be set.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Value	Comments	100	Rainfall is evenly distributed among all subintervals in a rainy interval. This is the default option.	101	Rainfall is evenly distributed among among RainAmongN subintervals in a rainy interval – also requires RainAmongN to be set.	102	Rainfall is evenly distributed among among RainAmongN subintervals in a rainy interval for different intensity bins – also requires MultRainAmongN and MultRainAmongNUpperI to be set.
Value	Comments									
100	Rainfall is evenly distributed among all subintervals in a rainy interval. This is the default option.									
101	Rainfall is evenly distributed among among RainAmongN subintervals in a rainy interval – also requires RainAmongN to be set.									
102	Rainfall is evenly distributed among among RainAmongN subintervals in a rainy interval for different intensity bins – also requires MultRainAmongN and MultRainAmongNUpperI to be set.									
<i>RainAmongN</i>	O	Specifies the number of subintervals (of length tt) over which to distribute rainfall in each interval (of length TT). Must be an integer value. Use with RainDisaggMethod = 101.								
<i>MultRainAmongN</i>	O	Specifies the number of subintervals (of length tt) over which to distribute rainfall in each interval (of length TT) for up to 5 intensity bins. Must take integer values. Use with RainDisaggMethod = 102. e.g. MultRainAmongN(1) = 5, MultRainAmongN(2) = 8, MultRainAmongN(3) = 12								
<i>MultRainAmongNUpperI</i>	O	Specifies upper limit for each intensity bin to apply MultRainAmongN. Any intensities above the highest specified intensity will use the last MultRainAmongN value and write a warning to warnings.txt. Use with RainDisaggMethod = 102. e.g. MultRainAmongNUpperI(1) = 0.5, MultRainAmongNUpperI(2) = 2.0, MultRainAmongNUpperI(3) = 50.0								
<i>DisaggMethodESTM</i>	O	<p>Specifies how ESTM-related temperatures in the input file are disaggregated to the model time step.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Value</th> <th>Comments</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Linear downscaling of averages.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Linear downscaling of instantaneous values.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Value	Comments	1	Linear downscaling of averages.	2	Linear downscaling of instantaneous values.		
Value	Comments									
1	Linear downscaling of averages.									
2	Linear downscaling of instantaneous values.									

netCDF-related options

N.B.: This feature is NOT enabled in the public release due to the dependency of netCDF library. Please contact the development team for assistance in enabling this feature if this feature is needed: [SUEWS mail list](#)

<i>ncMode</i>	O	Determine if the output files should be written in netCDF format.	
		Value	Comments
		0	▪ Output files are kept as plain text files (i.e., .txt).
		1	▪ Output files will be written in netCDF format (i.e., .nc).
<i>nRow</i>	O	Number of rows (e.g., 36) in the output layout (only applicable when ncMode=1).	
<i>nCol</i>	O	Number of columns (e.g., 47) in the output layout (only applicable when ncMode=1).	

SUEWS_SiteInfo.xlsm

The following text files provide SUEWS with information about the study area. These text files are stored as worksheets in **SUEWS_SiteInfo.xlsm** and can be either edited using Excel and then generated using the macro, or edited directly (see [Data Entry](#)). Please note this file is subject to possible changes from version to version due to new features, modifications, etc. Please be aware of using the correct copy of this worksheet that are always shipped with the SUEWS public release.

Use	Column
MU	Parameters which must be supplied and must be specific for the site/grid being run.
MD	Parameters which must be supplied and must be specific for the site/grid being run (but default values may be ok if these values are not known specifically for the site).
O	Parameters that are optional, depending on the model settings in RunControl. Set any parameters that are not used/not known to '-999'.
L	Codes that are used to link between the input files. These codes are required but their values are completely arbitrary, providing that they link the input files in the correct way. The user should choose these codes, bearing in mind that the codes they match up with in column 1 of the corresponding input file must be unique within that file. Codes must be integers. Note that the codes must match up with column 1 of the corresponding input file, even if those parameters are not used (in which case set all columns except column 1 to '-999' in the corresponding input file), otherwise the model run will fail.

SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt

For each year and each grid, site specific surface cover information and other input parameters is provided to SUEWS by **SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt**. The model currently requires a new row for each year of the model run. All rows in this file (before the two rows of '-9') will be read by the model and run. In this file the **column order is important**. '!' can be used to indicate comments in the file. Comments are not read by the programme so they can be used by the user to provide notes for their interpretation of the contents. This is strongly recommended.

No.	Use	Column name	Example	Description
1	MU	Grid	1	Grid number (any integer 0-2,147,483,647 (largest 4-byte integer)) identifying the current grid. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Grid numbers do not need to be consecutive and do not need to start at a particular value. ▪ Each grid must have a unique grid number. ▪ All grids must be present for all years. ▪ These grid numbers are referred to in GridConnections (columns 64-79) (N.B. GridConnections not currently implemented!) The two last lines in this column must read '-9' to indicate that the last lines have been reached (using two lines allows differences in computer file savings to be dealt with).
2	MU	Year	2011	Year [YYYY] Years must be continuous. If running multiple years, ensure the rows in SiteSelect.txt are arranged so that all grids for a particular year appear on consecutive lines (rather than grouping all years together for a particular grid).
3	MU	StartDLS	86	Start of the day light savings [DOY] See section on Day Light Savings .

4	MU	EndDLS	303	End of the day light savings [DOY] See section on Day Light Savings .
5	MU	lat	60.00	Latitude for the centre of the grid [decimal degrees] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use coordinate system WGS84. Positive values are northern hemisphere (negative southern hemisphere). Used in radiation calculations. Note, if the total modelled area is small the latitude and longitude could be the same for each grid but small differences in radiation will not be determined. If you are defining the latitude and longitude differently between grids make certain that you provide enough decimal places.
6	MU	lng	-18.20	Longitude for the centre of the grid [decimal degrees] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use coordinate system WGS84. For compatibility with GIS, negative values are to the west, positive values are to the east (e.g. Vancouver = -123.12; Shanghai = 121.47) Note this is a change of sign convention between v2016a and v2017a See latitude for more details.
7	MU	Timezone	0	Time zone [h] for site relative to UTC (east is positive). This should be set according to the times given in the meteorological forcing file(s).
8	MU	SurfaceArea	75.3	Area of the grid [ha].
9	MU	Alt	25.0	Altitude [m] Mean topographic height above sea-level. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Used for both the radiation and water flow between grids. (N.B. water flow between grids not currently implemented.)
10	MU	z	20.5	Height [m] of the meteorological forcing data. The most important height is that of the wind speed measurement. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> z must be greater than the displacement height. Forcing data should be representative of the local-scale, i.e. above the height of the roughness elements.
11	MD	id	1	Day [DOY] Not used: set to 1 in this version.
12	MD	ih	0	Hour [H] Not used: set to 0 in this version.
13	MD	imin	0	Minute [M] Not used: set to 0 in this version.
14	MU	Fr_Paved	0.20	Surface cover fraction of paved surfaces [-] Areal cover fraction of paved surfaces (roads, pavements, car parks). e.g. 20% of the grid is covered with paved surfaces. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Columns 14 to 20 must sum to 1.
15	MU	Fr_Bldgs	0.20	Surface cover fraction of buildings [-]
16	MU	Fr_EveTr	0.10	Surface cover fraction of evergreen trees and shrubs [-]
17	MU	Fr_DecTr	0.10	Surface cover fraction of deciduous trees and shrubs [-]
18	MU	Fr_Grass	0.30	Surface cover fraction of grass [-]
19	MU	Fr_Bsoil	0.05	Surface cover fraction of bare soil or unmanaged land [-]
20	MU	Fr_Water	0.05	Surface cover fraction of open water [-] (e.g. river, lakes, ponds, swimming pools)
21	MU	IrrFr_EveTr	0.50	Fraction of evergreen trees that are irrigated [-] e.g. 50% of the evergreen trees/shrubs are irrigated
22	MU	IrrFr_DecTr	0.20	Fraction of deciduous trees that are irrigated [-]
23	MU	IrrFr_Grass	0.70	Fraction of grass that is irrigated [-]
24	MU	H_Bldgs	10	Mean building height [m]
25	MU	H_EveTr	15	Mean height of evergreen trees [m]

26	MU	H_DecTr	15	Mean height of deciduous trees [m]
27	O	z0	0.6	Roughness length for momentum [m] Value supplied here is used if RoughLenMomMethod = 1 in <u>RunControl.nml</u> ; otherwise set to '-999' and a value will be calculated by the model (RoughLenMomMethod = 2, 3).
28	O	zd	1.5	Zero-plane displacement [m] Value supplied here is used if RoughLenMomMethod = 1 in <u>RunControl.nml</u> ; otherwise set to '-999' and a value will be calculated by the model (RoughLenMomMethod = 2, 3).
29	O	FAI_Bldgs	0.1	Frontal area index for buildings [-] Required if RoughLenMomMethod = 3 in <u>RunControl.nml</u> .
30	O	FAI_EveTr	0.2	Frontal area index for evergreen trees [-] Required if RoughLenMomMethod = 3 in <u>RunControl.nml</u> .
31	O	FAI_DecTr	0.2	Frontal area index for deciduous trees [-] Required if RoughLenMomMethod = 3 in <u>RunControl.nml</u> .
32	O	PopDensDay	30.7	Daytime population density (i.e. workers, tourists) [people ha ⁻¹] Population density is required if AnthropHeatMethod = 2 in <u>RunControl.nml</u> . The model will use the average of daytime and night-time population densities, unless only one is provided. If daytime population density is unknown, set to -999.
33	O	PopDensNight	10.2	Night-time population density (i.e. residents) [people ha ⁻¹] Population density is required if AnthropHeatMethod = 2 in <u>RunControl.nml</u> . The model will use the average of daytime and night-time population densities, unless only one is provided. If night-time population density is unknown, set to -999.
34	O	TrafficRate		Traffic rate [veh km m ⁻² s ⁻¹] Can be used for CO2 flux calculation. Do not use in v2017a - set to -999
35	O	BuildEnergyUse		Building energy use [W m ⁻²] Can be used for CO2 flux calculation. Do not use in v2017a - set to -999
36	L	Code_Paved	331	Code for Paved surface characteristics Provides the link to column 1 of SUEWS_NonVeg.txt, which contains the attributes describing paved areas in this grid for this year. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_NonVeg.txt. e.g. 331 means use the characteristics specified in the row of input file SUEWS_NonVeg.txt which has 331 in column 1 (Code).
37	L	Code_Bldgs	332	Code for Bldgs surface characteristics Provides the link to column 1 of SUEWS_NonVeg.txt, which contains the attributes describing buildings in this grid for this year. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_NonVeg.txt.
38	L	Code_EveTr	331	Code for EveTr surface characteristics Provides the link to column 1 of SUEWS_Veg.txt, which contains the attributes describing evergreen trees and shrubs in this grid for this year. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_Veg.txt.
39	L	Code_DecTr	332	Code for DecTr surface characteristics Provides the link to column 1 of SUEWS_Veg.txt, which contains the attributes describing deciduous trees and shrubs in this grid for this year. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_Veg.txt.
40	L	Code_Grass	333	Code for Grass surface characteristics

				Provides the link to column 1 of SUEWS_Veg.txt, which contains the attributes describing grass surfaces in this grid for this year. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_Veg.txt.
41	L	Code_Bsoil	333	Code for BSoil surface characteristics Provides the link to column 1 of SUEWS_NonVeg.txt, which contains the attributes describing bare soil in this grid for this year. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_NonVeg.txt.
42	L	Code_Water	331	Code for Water surface characteristics Provides the link to column 1 of SUEWS_Water.txt, which contains the attributes describing open water in this grid for this year. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_Water.txt.
43	MD	LUMPS_DrRate	0.25	Drainage rate of bucket for LUMPS [mm h ⁻¹] Used for LUMPS surface wetness control. Default recommended value of 0.25 mm h ⁻¹ from Loridan et al. (2011) ^[51] .
44	MD	LUMPS_Cover	1	Limit when surface totally covered with water [mm] Used for LUMPS surface wetness control. Default recommended value of 1 mm from Loridan et al. (2011) ^[51] .
45	MD	LUMPS_MaxRes	10	Maximum water bucket reservoir [mm] Used for LUMPS surface wetness control. Default recommended value of 10 mm from Loridan et al. (2011) ^[51] .
46	MD	NARP_Trans	1	Atmospheric transmissivity for NARP [-] Value must in the range 0-1. Default recommended value of 1.
47	L	CondCode	33	Code for surface conductance parameters Provides the link to column 1 of SUEWS_Conductance.txt, which contains the parameters for the Jarvis (1976) parameterisation of surface conductance. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_Conductance.txt. e.g. 33 means use the characteristics specified in the row of input file SUEWS_Conductance.txt which has 33 in column 1 (Code).
48	L	SnowCode	33	Code for snow surface characteristics Provides the link to column 1 of SUEWS_Snow.txt, which contains the attributes describing snow surfaces in this grid for this year. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_Snow.txt.
49	L	SnowClearingProfWD	1	Code for snow clearing profile (weekdays) Provides the link to column 1 of SUEWS_Profiles.txt. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_Profiles.txt. e.g. 1 means use the characteristics specified in the row of input file SUEWS_Profiles.txt which has 1 in column 1 (Code).
50	L	SnowClearingProfWE	1	Code for snow clearing profile (weekends) Provides the link to column 1 of SUEWS_Profiles.txt. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_Profiles.txt. e.g. 1 means use the characteristics specified in the row of input file SUEWS_Profiles.txt which has 1 in column 1 (Code). Providing the same code for SnowClearingProfWD and SnowClearingProfWE would link to the same row in SUEWS_Profiles.txt, i.e. the same profile would be used for weekdays and weekends.
51	L	AnthropogenicCode	33	Code for modelling anthropogenic heat flux Provides the link to column 1 of SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt, which contains the model

				coefficients for estimation of the anthropogenic heat flux (used if AnthropHeatChoice = 1, 2 in RunControl.nml). Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt.
52	L	EnergyUseProfWD	333	Code for energy use profile (weekdays) Provides the link to column 1 of SUEWS_Profiles.txt. Look the codes Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_Profiles.txt.
53	L	EnergyUseProfWE	334	Code for energy use profile (weekends) Provides the link to column 1 of SUEWS_Profiles.txt. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_Profiles.txt.
54	L	ActivityProfWD	333	Code for human activity profile (weekdays) Provides the link to column 1 of SUEWS_Profiles.txt. Look the codes Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_Profiles.txt. Used for CO2 flux calculation - not used in v2017a
55	L	ActivityProfWE	333	Code for human activity profile (weekends) Provides the link to column 1 of SUEWS_Profiles.txt. Look the codes Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_Profiles.txt. Used for CO2 flux calculation - not used in v2017a
56	L	IrrigationCode	33	Code for modelling irrigation Provides the link to column 1 of SUEWS_Irrigation.txt, which contains the model coefficients for estimation of the water use (used if WU_Choice = 0 in RunControl.nml). Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_Irrigation.txt.
57	L	WaterUseProfManuWD	335	Code for water use profile (manual irrigation, weekdays) Provides the link to column 1 of SUEWS_Profiles.txt. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_Profiles.txt.
58	L	WaterUseProfManuWE	336	Code for water use profile (manual irrigation, weekends) Provides the link to column 1 of SUEWS_Profiles.txt. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_Profiles.txt.
59	L	WaterUseProfAutoWD	337	Code for water use profile (automatic irrigation, weekdays) Provides the link to column 1 of SUEWS_Profiles.txt. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_Profiles.txt.
60	L	WaterUseProfAutoWE	338	Code for water use profile (automatic irrigation, weekends) Provides the link to column 1 of SUEWS_Profiles.txt. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_Profiles.txt.
61	MD	FlowChange	0	Difference in input and output flows for water surface [mm h ⁻¹] Used to indicate river or stream flow through the grid. Currently not fully tested!
62	MD,MU	RunoffToWater	0.1	Fraction of above-ground runoff flowing to water surface during flooding [-] Value must be in the range 0-1. Fraction of above-ground runoff that can flow to the water surface in the case of flooding.
63	MD,MU	PipeCapacity	100	Storage capacity of pipes [mm] Runoff amounting to less than the value specified here is assumed to be removed by pipes.
64	MD,MU	GridConnection1of8	2	Number of the grid where water can flow to [-] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The next 8 pairs of columns specify the water flow between grids.

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The first column of each pair specifies the grid that the water flows to (from the current grid, column 1); the second column of each pair specifies the fraction of water that flow to that grid. ▪ The fraction (i.e. amount) of water transferred may be estimated based on elevation, the length of connecting surface between grids, presence of walls, etc. ▪ Water cannot flow from the current grid to the same grid, so the grid number here must be different to the grid number in column 1. Water can flow to a maximum of 8 other grids. ▪ If there is no water flow between grids, or a single grid is run, set to 0. ▪ See section on Grid Connections <p>Not currently implemented!</p>
65	MD,MU	Fraction1of8	0.2	Fraction of water that can flow to the grid specified in previous column [-]
66	MD,MU	GridConnection2of8	0	Number of the grid where water can flow to
67	MD,MU	Fraction2of8	0	Fraction of water that can flow to the grid specified in previous column [-]
68	MD,MU	GridConnection3of8	0	Number of the grid where water can flow to
69	MD,MU	Fraction3of8	0	Fraction of water that can flow to the grid specified in previous column [-]
70	MD,MU	GridConnection4of8	0	Number of the grid where water can flow to
71	MD,MU	Fraction4of8	0	Fraction of water that can flow to the grid specified in previous column [-]
72	MD,MU	GridConnection5of8	0	Number of the grid where water can flow to
73	MD,MU	Fraction5of8	0	Fraction of water that can flow to the grid specified in previous column [-]
74	MD,MU	GridConnection6of8	0	Number of the grid where water can flow to
75	MD,MU	Fraction6of8	0	Fraction of water that can flow to the grid specified in previous column [-]
76	MD,MU	GridConnection7of8	0	Number of the grid where water can flow to
77	MD,MU	Fraction7of8	0	Fraction of water that can flow to the grid specified in previous column [-]
78	MD,MU	GridConnection8of8	0	Number of the grid where water can flow to
79	MD,MU	Fraction8of8	0	Fraction of water that can flow to the grid specified in previous column [-]
80	L	WithinGridPavedCode	331	Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from Paved surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt .
81	L	WithinGridBldgsCode	332	Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from Bldgs surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt .
82	L	WithinGridEveTrCode	333	Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from EveTr surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt .
83	L	WithinGridDecTrCode	334	Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from DecTr surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt .

84	L	WithinGridGrassCode	335	Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from Grass surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt.
85	L	WithinGridBSoilCode	336	Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from BSoil surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt.
86	L	WithinGridWaterCode	337	Code that links to the fraction of water that flows from Water surfaces to surfaces in columns 2-10 of SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt.
87	MU	AreaWall	1.08	Area of wall within grid (needed for ESTM calculation).
88	MU	Fr_ESTMClass_Paved1		Fraction of paved surface classified as ESTM class 1 ▪ Columns 88-90 must add up to 1
89	MU	Fr_ESTMClass_Paved2		Fraction of paved surface classified as ESTM class 2 ▪ Columns 88-90 must add up to 1
90	MU	Fr_ESTMClass_Paved3		Fraction of paved surface classified as ESTM class 3 ▪ Columns 88-90 must add up to 1
91	L	Code_ESTMClass_Paved1		Code linking to SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt
92	L	Code_ESTMClass_Paved2		Code linking to SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt
93	L	Code_ESTMClass_Paved3		Code linking to SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt
94	MU	Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs1		Fraction of building surface classified as ESTM class 1 ▪ Columns 94-98 must add up to 1
95	MU	Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs2		Fraction of building surface classified as ESTM class 2 ▪ Columns 94-98 must add up to 1
96	MU	Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs3		Fraction of building surface classified as ESTM class 3 ▪ Columns 94-98 must add up to 1
97	MU	Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs4		Fraction of building surface classified as ESTM class 4 ▪ Columns 94-98 must add up to 1
98	MU	Fr_ESTMClass_Bldgs5		Fraction of building surface classified as ESTM class 5 ▪ Columns 94-98 must add up to 1
99	L	Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs1		Code linking to SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt
100	L	Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs2		Code linking to SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt
101	L	Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs3		Code linking to SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt
102	L	Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs4		Code linking to SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt
103	L	Code_ESTMClass_Bldgs5		Code linking to SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt

Day Light Savings (DLS)

The dates for DLS normally vary each year and country as they are often associated with a specific set of Sunday mornings at the beginning of summer and autumn. Note it is important to remember leap years. You can check <http://www.timeanddate.com/time/dst/> for your city.

If DLS does not occur give a start and end day immediately after it. Make certain the dummy dates are correct for the hemisphere:

```
for northern hemisphere, use: 180 181
for southern hemisphere, use: 365 1
```

Example:	Year	start of daylight savings	end of daylight savings
when running multiple years (in this case 2008 and 2009 in Canada)	2008	170	240
	2009	172	242

Grid Connections (water flow between grids)

N.B. not currently implemented - columns 64-79 of SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt can be set to zero.

This section gives an example of water flow between grids, calculated based on the relative elevation of the grids and length of the connecting surface between adjacent grids. For the square grids in the figure, water flow is assumed to be zero between diagonally adjacent grids, as the length of connecting surface linking the grids is very small. Model grids need not be square or the same size.

The table gives example values for the grid connections part of SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt for the grids shown in the figure. For each row, only water flowing out of the current grid is entered (e.g. water flows from 234 to 236 and 237, with a larger proportion of water flowing to 237 because of the greater length of connecting surface between 234 and 237 than between 234 and 236. No water is assumed to flow between 234 and 233 or 235 because there is no elevation difference between these grids. Grids 234 and 238 are at the same elevation and only connect at a point, so no water flows between them. Water enters grid 234 from grids 230, 231 and 232 as these are more elevated.

Example grid connections showing water flow between grids. Arrows indicate the water flow in to and out of grid 234, but note that only only water flowing out of each grid is entered in SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt.

Grid	GridConnection 1o8	Fraction1o8	GridConnection 2o8	Fraction2o8	GridConnection 3o8	Fraction3o8	GridConnection 4o8	Fraction4o8	GridConnection 5o8	Fraction5o8	GridConnection 6o8	Fraction6o8	GridConnection 7o8	Fraction7o8	GridConnection 8o8	Fraction8o8
230	233	0.90	234	0.10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
231	234	1.00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
232	234	0.20	235	0.80	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
233	236	1.00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
234	236	0.10	237	0.90	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
235	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
236	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
237	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
238	237	1.0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Example values for the grid connections part of SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt for the grids.

SUEWS_NonVeg.txt

SUEWS_NonVeg.txt specifies the characteristics for the non-vegetated surface cover types (Paved, Bldgs, BSoil) by linking codes in column 1 of SUEWS_NonVeg.txt to the codes specified in SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt (Code_Paved, Code_Bldgs, Code_BSoil). Each row should correspond to a particular surface type. For suggestions on how to complete this table, see: Typical Values.

No.	Use	Column name	Example	Description
1	L	Code	331 ----- 332 ----- 333	Code linking to SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt for paved surfaces (Code_Paved), buildings (Code_Bldgs) and bare soil surfaces (Code_BSoil). Value of integer is arbitrary but must match codes specified in SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt.
2	MU	AlbedoMin	0-1	Minimum albedo of this surface [-] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Effective surface albedo (middle of the day value) for wintertime (not including snow). View factors should be taken into account. Not currently used for non-vegetated surfaces – set the same as AlbedoMax.
3	MU	AlbedoMax	0-1	Maximum albedo of this surface [-] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Effective surface albedo (middle of the day value) for summertime. View factors should be taken into account.
4	MU	Emissivity	0-1	Emissivity of this surface [-] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Effective surface emissivity. View factors should be taken into account.
5	MD	StorageMin		Minimum water storage capacity of this surface [mm] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minimum water storage capacity for upper surfaces (i.e. canopy). Min/max values are to account for seasonal variation (e.g. leaf-on/leaf-off differences for vegetated surfaces). Not currently used for non-vegetated surfaces - set the same as StorageMax. <p>Example values [mm]</p> <p>0.48 Paved 0.25 Bldgs 0.80 BSoil</p>
6	MD	StorageMax		Maximum water storage capacity of this surface [mm] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maximum water storage capacity for upper surfaces (i.e. canopy) Min and max values are to account for seasonal variation (e.g. leaf-on/leaf-off differences for vegetated surfaces). Not currently used for non-vegetated surfaces - set the same as StorageMin. <p>Example values [mm]</p> <p>0.48 Paved 0.25 Bldgs 0.80 BSoil</p>
7	MD	WetThreshold		Threshold for a completely wet surface [mm] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Depth of water which determines whether evaporation occurs from a partially wet or completely wet surface. <p>Example values [mm]</p> <p>0.6 Paved 0.6 Bldgs 1.0 BSoil</p>
8	MD	StateLimit		Upper limit to the surface state [mm] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Currently only used for the water surface
9	MD	DrainageEq	1, 2, 3	Drainage equation to use for this surface. Options

			<p>1 Falk and Niemczynowicz (1978)^[32]</p> <p>2 Halldin et al. (1979)^[33] (Rutter eqn corrected for $c=0$, see Calder & Wright (1986)^[34])</p> <p>3 Falk and Niemczynowicz (1978)^[32]</p> <p>Recommended^[3] for BSoil</p> <p>Recommended^[3] for Paved and Bldgs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Coefficients are specified in the following two columns. 								
10	MD	DrainageCoef1	<p>Coefficient for drainage equation [units vary according to DrainageEq specified in previous column]</p> <p>Example values</p> <table border="0"> <tr> <td>10</td> <td>Coefficient D0 [mm h⁻¹]</td> <td>3</td> <td>Recommended^[3] for Paved and Bldgs</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0.013</td> <td>Coefficient D0 [mm h⁻¹]</td> <td>2</td> <td>Recommended^[3] for BSoil</td> </tr> </table>	10	Coefficient D0 [mm h ⁻¹]	3	Recommended ^[3] for Paved and Bldgs	0.013	Coefficient D0 [mm h ⁻¹]	2	Recommended ^[3] for BSoil
10	Coefficient D0 [mm h ⁻¹]	3	Recommended ^[3] for Paved and Bldgs								
0.013	Coefficient D0 [mm h ⁻¹]	2	Recommended ^[3] for BSoil								
11	MD	DrainageCoef2	<p>Coefficient for drainage equation [units vary according to DrainageEq specified in previous column]</p> <p>Example values</p> <table border="0"> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Coefficient b [-]</td> <td>3</td> <td>Recommended^[3] for Paved and Bldgs</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1.71</td> <td>Coefficient b [mm⁻¹]</td> <td>2</td> <td>Recommended^[3] for BSoil</td> </tr> </table>	3	Coefficient b [-]	3	Recommended ^[3] for Paved and Bldgs	1.71	Coefficient b [mm ⁻¹]	2	Recommended ^[3] for BSoil
3	Coefficient b [-]	3	Recommended ^[3] for Paved and Bldgs								
1.71	Coefficient b [mm ⁻¹]	2	Recommended ^[3] for BSoil								
12	L	SoilTypeCode	<p>Code for soil characteristics below this surface</p> <p>Provides the link to column 1 of SUEWS_Soil.txt, which contains the attributes describing sub-surface soil for this surface type. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_Soil.txt.</p>								
13	O	SnowLimPatch	<p>Maximum SWE [mm]</p> <p>Limit of snow water equivalent when the surface is fully covered with snow.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Not needed if SnowUse = 0 in RunControl.nml. <p>Example values [mm]</p> <p>190 Paved Järvi et al. (2014)^[15]</p> <p>190 Bldgs Järvi et al. (2014)^[15]</p> <p>190 BSoil Järvi et al. (2014)^[15]</p>								
14	O	SnowLimRemove	<p>SWE when snow is removed from this surface [mm]</p> <p>Limit of snow water equivalent when snow is removed from paved surfaces and buildings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Not needed if SnowUse = 0 in RunControl.nml. ▪ Currently not implemented for BSoil surface <p>Example values [mm]</p> <p>40 Paved Järvi et al. (2014)^[15]</p> <p>100 Bldgs Järvi et al. (2014)^[15]</p>								
15	L	OHMCode_SummerWet	<p>Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in summer.</p> <p>Links to SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt.</p>								
16	L	OHMCode_SummerDry	<p>Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in summer.</p> <p>Links to SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt.</p>								

17	L	OHMCode_WinterWet		Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in winter. Links to SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt .
18	L	OHMCode_WinterDry		Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in winter. Links to SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt .
19	MD	OHMThresh_SW	10	Temperature threshold determining whether summer/winter OHM coefficients are applied [deg C] If 5-day running mean air temperature is greater than or equal to this threshold, OHM coefficients for summertime are applied; otherwise coefficients for wintertime are applied.
20	MD	OHMThresh_WD	0.9	Soil moisture threshold determining whether wet/dry OHM coefficients are applied [-] If soil moisture (as a proportion of maximum soil moisture capacity) exceeds this threshold for bare soil and vegetated surfaces, OHM coefficients for wet conditions are applied; otherwise coefficients for dry conditions are applied. Note that OHM coefficients for wet conditions are applied if the surface is wet. Not actually used for building and paved surfaces (as impervious).
21	L	ESTMCode		Code for ESTM coefficients to use for this surface. Links to SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt . <ul style="list-style-type: none"> For paved and building surfaces, it is possible to specify multiple codes per grid (3 for paved, 5 for buildings) using SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt. In this case, set ESTMCode here to zero.
22	MU	AnOHM_Cp		Volumetric heat capacity for this surface to use in AnOHM [J m ⁻³]
23	MU	AnOHM_Kk		Thermal conductivity for this surface to use in AnOHM [W m K ⁻¹]
24	MU	AnOHM_Ch		Bulk transfer coefficient for this surface to use in AnOHM [-]

SUEWS_Veg.txt

SUEWS_Veg.txt specifies the characteristics for the vegetated surface cover types (EveTr, DecTr, Grass) by linking codes in column 1 of SUEWS_Veg.txt to the codes specified in [SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt](#) (Code_EveTr, Code_DecTr, Code_Grass). Each row should correspond to a particular surface type. For suggestions on how to complete this table, see: [Typical Values](#).

No.	Use	Column name	Example	Description
1	L	Code	331 ----- 332 ----- 333	Code linking to SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt for evergreen trees and shrubs (Code_EveTr), deciduous trees and shrubs (Code_DecTr) and grass surfaces (Code_Grass). Value of integer is arbitrary but must match codes specified in SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt .
2	MU	AlbedoMin	0-1	Minimum albedo of this surface [-] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Effective surface albedo (middle of the day value) for wintertime (not including snow), leaf-off. View factors should be taken into account.

			<p>Example values [-] 0.10 EveTr Oke (1987)^[35] 0.18 DecTr Oke (1987)^[35] 0.21 Grass Oke (1987)^[35]</p>
3	MU	AlbedoMax	<p>0-1</p> <p>Maxmium albedo of this surface [-]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Effective surface albedo (middle of the day value) for summertime, full leaf-on. View factors should be taken into account. <p>Example values [-] 0.10 EveTr Oke (1987)^[35] 0.18 DecTr Oke (1987)^[35] 0.21 Grass Oke (1987)^[35]</p>
4	MU	Emissivity	<p>0-1</p> <p>Emissivity of this surface [-]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Effective surface emissivity. View factors should be taken into account. <p>Example values [-] 0.98 EveTr Oke (1987)^[35] 0.98 DecTr Oke (1987)^[35] 0.93 Grass Oke (1987)^[35]</p>
5	MD	StorageMin	<p>Minimum water storage capacity of this surface [mm]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minimum water storage capacity for upper surfaces (i.e. canopy). Min/max values are to account for seasonal variation (e.g. leaf-off/leaf-on differences for vegetated surfaces). <p>Example values [mm] 1.3 EveTr Breuer et al. (2003)^[36] 0.3 DecTr Breuer et al. (2003)^[36] 1.9 Grass Breuer et al. (2003)^[36]</p>
6	MD	StorageMax	<p>Maximum water storage capacity of this surface [mm]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maximum water storage capacity for upper surfaces (i.e. canopy) Min/max values are to account for seasonal variation (e.g. leaf-off/leaf-on differences for vegetated surfaces) Only used for DecTr surfaces - set EveTr and Grass values the same as StorageMin. <p>Example values [mm] 1.3 EveTr Breuer et al. (2003)^[36] 0.8 DecTr Breuer et al. (2003)^[36] 1.9 Grass Breuer et al. (2003)^[36]</p>
7	MD	WetThreshold	<p>Threshold for a completely wet surface [mm]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Depth of water which determines whether evaporation occurs from a partially wet or completely wet surface. <p>Example values [mm] 1.8 EveTr 1.0 DecTr 2.0 Grass</p>
8	MD	StateLimit	<p>Upper limit to the surface state [mm]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Currently only used for the water surface
9	MD	DrainageEq	<p>1, 2, 3</p> <p>Drainage equation to use for this surface.</p>

			<p>Options</p> <p>1 Falk and Niemczynowicz (1978)^[32]</p> <p>2 Halldin et al. (1979)^[33] (Rutter eqn corrected for c=0, see Calder & Wright (1986)^[34])</p> <p>3 Falk and Niemczynowicz (1978)^[32]</p> <p>Recommended^[3] for EveTr, DecTr, Grass (unirrigated)</p> <p>Recommended^[3] for Grass (irrigated)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Coefficients are specified in the following two columns. 								
10	MD	DrainageCoef1	<p>Coefficient for drainage equation [units vary according to DrainageEq specified in previous column]</p> <p>Example values</p> <table border="0"> <tr> <td>10</td> <td>Coefficient D0 [mm h⁻¹]</td> <td>3</td> <td>Recommended^[3] for Grass (irrigated)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0.013</td> <td>Coefficient D0 [mm h⁻¹]</td> <td>2</td> <td>Recommended^[3] for EveTr, DecTr, Grass (unirrigated)</td> </tr> </table>	10	Coefficient D0 [mm h ⁻¹]	3	Recommended ^[3] for Grass (irrigated)	0.013	Coefficient D0 [mm h ⁻¹]	2	Recommended ^[3] for EveTr, DecTr, Grass (unirrigated)
10	Coefficient D0 [mm h ⁻¹]	3	Recommended ^[3] for Grass (irrigated)								
0.013	Coefficient D0 [mm h ⁻¹]	2	Recommended ^[3] for EveTr, DecTr, Grass (unirrigated)								
11	MD	DrainageCoef2	<p>Coefficient for drainage equation [units vary according to DrainageEq specified in previous column]</p> <p>Example values</p> <table border="0"> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Coefficient b [-]</td> <td>3</td> <td>Recommended^[3] for Grass (irrigated)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1.71</td> <td>Coefficient b [mm⁻¹]</td> <td>2</td> <td>Recommended^[3] for EveTr, DecTr, Grass (unirrigated)</td> </tr> </table>	3	Coefficient b [-]	3	Recommended ^[3] for Grass (irrigated)	1.71	Coefficient b [mm ⁻¹]	2	Recommended ^[3] for EveTr, DecTr, Grass (unirrigated)
3	Coefficient b [-]	3	Recommended ^[3] for Grass (irrigated)								
1.71	Coefficient b [mm ⁻¹]	2	Recommended ^[3] for EveTr, DecTr, Grass (unirrigated)								
12	L	SoilTypeCode	<p>Code for soil characteristics below this surface</p> <p>Provides the link to column 1 of SUEWS_Soil.txt, which contains the attributes describing sub-surface soil for this surface type. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_Soil.txt.</p>								
13	O	SnowLimPatch	<p>Maximum SWE [mm]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Limit of snow water equivalent when the surface surface is fully covered with snow. ▪ Not needed if SnowUse = 0 in RunControl.nml. <p>Example values [mm]</p> <p>190 EveTr Järvi et al. (2014)^[15]</p> <p>190 DecTr Järvi et al. (2014)^[15]</p> <p>190 Grass Järvi et al. (2014)^[15]</p>								
14	MU	BaseT	<p>Base temperature for initiating growing degree days for leaf growth [°C]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ See section 2.2 Järvi et al. (2011); Appendix A Järvi et al. (2014). <p>Example values [°C]</p> <p>5 EveTr Järvi et al. (2011)^[11]</p> <p>5 DecTr Järvi et al. (2011)^[11]</p> <p>5 Grass Järvi et al. (2011)^[11]</p>								
15	MU	BaseTe	<p>Base temperature for initiating senescence degree days for leaf off [°C]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ See section 2.2 Järvi et al. (2011)^[11]; Appendix A Järvi et al. (2014)^[15]. <p>Example values [°C]</p> <p>10 EveTr Järvi et al. (2011)^[11]</p>								

			10 DecTr Järvi et al. (2011) ^[1] 10 Grass Järvi et al. (2011) ^[1]
16	MU	GDDFull	<p>Growing degree days needed for full capacity of the leaf area index [°C]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> This should be checked carefully for your study area using modelled LAI from the <u>DailyState</u> output file compared to known behaviour in the study area. See section 2.2 Järvi et al. (2011)^[1]; Appendix A Järvi et al. (2014)^[15] for more details. <p>Example values [°C] 300 EveTr Järvi et al. (2011)^[1] 300 DecTr Järvi et al. (2011)^[1] 300 Grass Järvi et al. (2011)^[1]</p>
17	MU	SDDFull	<p>Senescence degree days needed to initiate leaf off [°C]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> This should be checked carefully for your study area using modelled LAI from the <u>DailyState</u> output file compared to known behaviour in the study area. See section 2.2 Järvi et al. (2011)^[1]; Appendix A Järvi et al. (2014)^[15] for more details. <p>Example values [°C] -450 EveTr Järvi et al. (2011)^[1] -450 DecTr Järvi et al. (2011)^[1] -450 Grass Järvi et al. (2011)^[1]</p>
18	MD	LAIMin	<p>Minimum leaf area index [m² m⁻²]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> leaf-off wintertime value <p>Example values [m² m⁻²] 4.0 EveTr Järvi et al. (2011)^[1] 1.0 DecTr Järvi et al. (2011)^[1] 1.6 Grass Grimmond and Oke (1991)^[3] and references therein</p>
19	MD	LAIMax	<p>Maximum leaf area index [m² m⁻²]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> full leaf-on summertime value <p>Example values [m² m⁻²] 5.1 EveTr Breuer et al. (2003)^[36] 5.5 DecTr Breuer et al. (2003)^[36] 5.9 Grass Breuer et al. (2003)^[36]</p>
20	MD	PorosityMin	0.2
			<p>Minimum porosity [-]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> leaf-off wintertime value Used only for DecTr (can affect roughness calculation)
21	MD	PorosityMax	0.6
			<p>Maximum porosity [-]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> full leaf-on summertime value Used only for DecTr (can affect roughness calculation)
22	MD	MaxConductance	<p>Maximum conductance for each surface [mm s⁻¹]</p> <p>Used to calculate the surface conductance using the Jarvis (1976)^[37] model. See Eq 15 Järvi et al. (2011)^[1] or Eq 8 Ward et al. (2016)^[2].</p> <p>Example values [mm s⁻¹] 7.4 EveTr Järvi et al. (2011)^[1] 11.7 DecTr Järvi et al. (2011)^[1]</p>

			33.1 Grass (unirrigated) Järvi et al. (2011) ^[1] 40.0 Grass (irrigated) Järvi et al. (2011) ^[1]
23	MD	LAIEq	0, 1 LAI equation to use for this surface. Options 0 Järvi et al. (2011) ^[1] 1 Järvi et al. (2014) ^[15] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Coefficients are specified in the following four columns. ▪ N.B. North and South hemispheres are treated slightly differently.
24	MD	LeafGrowthPower1	Coefficient (power) for leaf growth [-] See Appendix A Järvi et al. (2014) ^[15] for more details. Example values LAIEq 0.03 Järvi et al. (2011) ^[1] 0 0.04 Järvi et al. (2014) ^[15] 1
25	MD	LeafGrowthPower2	Constant in the leaf growth equation [$^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$] See Appendix A Järvi et al. (2014) ^[15] for more details. Example values [$^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$] LAIEq 0.0005 Järvi et al. (2011) ^[1] 0 0.0010 Järvi et al. (2014) ^[15] 1
26	MD	LeafOffPower1	Coefficient (power) for leaf off [-] See Appendix A Järvi et al. (2014) ^[15] for more details. Example values LAIEq 0.03 Järvi et al. (2011) ^[1] 0 -1.5 Järvi et al. (2014) ^[15] 1
27	MD	LeafOffPower2	Constant in the leaf off equation [$^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$] See Appendix A Järvi et al. (2014) ^[15] for more details. Example values [$^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$] LAIEq 0.0005 Järvi et al. (2011) ^[1] 0 0.0015 Järvi et al. (2014) ^[15] 1
28	L	OHMCode_SummerWet	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in summer. Links to SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt .
29	L	OHMCode_SummerDry	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in summer. Links to SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt .
30	L	OHMCode_WinterWet	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in winter. Links to SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt .
31	L	OHMCode_WinterDry	Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in winter. Links to SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt .
32	MD	OHMThresh_SW	10 Temperature threshold determining whether summer/winter OHM coefficients are applied [deg C] If 5-day running mean air temperature is greater than or equal to this threshold, OHM coefficients for

			summertime are applied; otherwise coefficients for wintertime are applied.	
33	MD	OHMThresh_WD	0.9	Soil moisture threshold determining whether wet/dry OHM coefficients are applied [-] If soil moisture (as a proportion of maximum soil moisture capacity) exceeds this threshold for bare soil and vegetated surfaces, OHM coefficients for wet conditions are applied; otherwise coefficients for dry coefficients are applied. Note that OHM coefficients for wet conditions are applied if the surface is wet.
34	L	ESTMCode		Code for ESTM coefficients to use for this surface. Links to SUEWS_ESTMcoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_ESTMcoefficients.txt .
35	MU	AnOHM_Cp		Volumetric heat capacity for this surface to use in AnOHM [J m^{-3}]
36	MU	AnOHM_Kk		Thermal conductivity for this surface to use in AnOHM [W m K^{-1}]
37	MU	AnOHM_Ch		Bulk transfer coefficient for this surface to use in AnOHM [-]

SUEWS_Water.txt

SUEWS_Water.txt specifies the characteristics for the water surface cover type by linking codes in column 1 of SUEWS_Water.txt to the codes specified in SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt (Code_Water).

No.	Use	Column name	Example	Description
1	L	Code	331	Code linking to SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt for water surfaces (Code_Water). Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt .
2	MU	AlbedoMin	0-1	Minimum albedo of this surface [-] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> View factors should be taken into account. Not currently used for water surface - set same as AlbedoMax.
3	MU	AlbedoMax	0-1	Albedo of this surface [-] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Effective albedo of the water surface. View factors should be taken into account. <p>Example values [-]</p> <p>0.1 Water Oke (1987)^[35]</p>
4	MU	Emissivity	0-1	Emissivity of this surface [-] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Effective surface emissivity. View factors should be taken into account <p>Example values [-]</p> <p>0.95 Water Oke (1987)^[35]</p>
5	MD	StorageMin		Minimum water storage capacity of this surface [mm]

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minimum water storage capacity for upper surfaces (i.e. canopy). Min/max values are to account for seasonal variation - not used for water surfaces. <p>Example values [mm]</p> <p>0.5 Water</p>
6	MD	StorageMax	<p>Maximum water storage capacity of this surface [mm]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maximum water storage capacity for upper surfaces (i.e. canopy) Min and max values are to account for seasonal variation - not used for water surfaces so set same as StorageMin.
7	MD	WetThreshold	<p>Threshold for a completely wet surface [mm]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Depth of water which determines whether evaporation occurs from a partially wet or completely wet surface. <p>Example values [mm]</p> <p>0.5 Water</p>
8	MU	StateLimit	<p>Upper limit to the surface state [mm]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Surface state cannot exceed this value. Set to a large value (e.g. 20000 mm = 20 m) if the water body is substantial (lake, river, etc) or a small value (e.g. 10 mm) if water bodies are very shallow (e.g. fountains). WaterDepth (column 9) must not exceed this value.
9	MU	WaterDepth	<p>Typical depth for the water surface [mm]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Set to a large value (e.g. 20000 mm = 20 m) if the water body is substantial (lake, river, etc) or a small value (e.g. 10 mm) if water bodies are very shallow (e.g. fountains). This value must not exceed StateLimit (column 8).
10	MD	DrainageEq	<p>Drainage equation to use for this surface.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not currently used for water surface.
11	MD	DrainageCoef1	<p>Coefficient for drainage equation [units vary according to equation]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not currently used for water surface
12	MD	DrainageCoef2	<p>Coefficient for drainage equation [units vary according to equation]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not currently used for water surface
13	L	OHMCode_SummerWet	<p>Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in summer.</p>

				Links to SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt .
14	L	OHMCode_SummerDry		Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in summer. Links to SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt .
15	L	OHMCode_WinterWet		Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in winter. Links to SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt .
16	L	OHMCode_WinterDry		Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in winter. Links to SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt .
17	MD	OHMThresh_SW	10	Temperature threshold determining whether summer/winter OHM coefficients are applied [deg C] If 5-day running mean air temperature is greater than or equal to this threshold, OHM coefficients for summertime are applied; otherwise coefficients for wintertime are applied.
18	MD	OHMThresh_WD	0.9	Soil moisture threshold determining whether wet/dry OHM coefficients are applied [-] If soil moisture (as a proportion of maximum soil moisture capacity) exceeds this threshold for bare soil and vegetated surfaces, OHM coefficients for wet conditions are applied; otherwise coefficients for dry coefficients are applied. Note that OHM coefficients for wet conditions are applied if the surface is wet. Not actually used for water surface (as no soil surface beneath).
19	L	ESTMCode		Code for ESTM coefficients to use for this surface. Links to SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt .
20	MU	AnOHM_Cp		Volumetric heat capacity for this surface to use in AnOHM [J m ⁻³]
21	MU	AnOHM_Kk		Thermal conductivity for this surface to use in AnOHM [W m K ⁻¹]
22	MU	AnOHM_Ch		Bulk transfer coefficient for this surface to use in AnOHM [-]

SUEWS_Snow.txt

SUEWS_Snow.txt specifies the characteristics for snow surfaces when SnowUse=1 in [RunControl.nml](#). If the snow part of the model is not run, fill this table with '-999' except for the first (Code) column and set

SnowUse=0 in RunControl.nml. For a detailed description of the variables, see Järvi et al. (2014)^[15]. In the current release SnowUse should be set to 0.

No.	Use	Column name	Example	Description
1	L	Code	331	Code linking to <u>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</u> for snow surfaces (SnowCode). Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt.
2	MU	RadMeltFactor	0.0016	Hourly radiation melt factor of snow [$\text{mm W}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$]
3	MU	TempMeltFactor	0.07	Hourly temperature melt factor of snow [$\text{mm } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$] (In previous model version, this parameter was 0.12)
4	MU	AlbedoMin	0-1	Minimum snow albedo [-] Example values [-] 0.18 Järvi et al. (2014) ^[15]
5	MU	AlbedoMax	0-1	Maximum snow albedo (fresh snow) [-] Example values [-] 0.85 Järvi et al. (2014) ^[15]
6	MU	Emissivity	0-1	Emissivity of this surface [-] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Effective surface emissivity. ▪ View factors should be taken into account Example values [-] 0.99 Järvi et al. (2014) ^[15]
7	MD	tau_a	0.018	Time constant for snow albedo aging in cold snow [-]
8	MD	tau_f	0.11	Time constant for snow albedo aging in melting snow [-]
9	MD	PrecipiLimAlb	2	Limit for hourly precipitation when the ground is fully covered with snow. Then snow albedo is reset to AlbedoMax [mm]
10	MD	snowDensMin	100	Fresh snow density [kg m^{-3}]
11	MD	snowDensMax	400	Maximum snow density [kg m^{-3}]
12	MD	tau_r	0.043	Time constant for snow density ageing [-]
13	MD	CRWMin	0.05	Minimum water holding capacity of snow [mm]
14	MD	CRWMax	0.20	Maximum water holding capacity of snow [mm]
15	MD	PrecipLimSnow	2.2	Temperature limit when precipitation falls as snow [$^\circ\text{C}$] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Auer (1974)^[38]
16	L	OHMCode_SummerWet		Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in summer. Links to <u>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</u> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt.
17	L	OHMCode_SummerDry		Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in summer. Links to <u>SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt</u> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt.
18	L	OHMCode_WinterWet		Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during wet conditions in winter.

				Links to SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt .
19	L	OHMCode_WinterDry		Code for OHM coefficients to use for this surface during dry conditions in winter. Links to SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt .
20	MD	OHMThresh_SW	10	Temperature threshold determining whether summer/winter OHM coefficients are applied [deg C] If 5-day running mean air temperature is greater than or equal to this threshold, OHM coefficients for summertime are applied; otherwise coefficients for wintertime are applied. Not actually used for Snow surface as winter wet conditions always assumed.
21	MD	OHMThresh_WD	0.9	Soil moisture threshold determining whether wet/dry OHM coefficients are applied [-] If soil moisture (as a proportion of maximum soil moisture capacity) exceeds this threshold for bare soil and vegetated surfaces, OHM coefficients for wet conditions are applied; otherwise coefficients for dry coefficients are applied. Note that OHM coefficients for wet conditions are applied if the surface is wet. Not actually used for Snow surface as winter wet conditions always assumed.
22	L	ESTMCode		Code for ESTM coefficients to use for this surface. Links to SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in column 1 of SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt . <ul style="list-style-type: none"> For paved and building surfaces, it is possible to specify multiple codes per grid (3 for paved, 5 for buildings) using SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt. In this case, set ESTM code here to zero.
23	MU	AnOHM_Cp		Volumetric heat capacity for this surface to use in AnOHM [J m ⁻³]
24	MU	AnOHM_Kk		Thermal conductivity for this surface to use in AnOHM [W m K ⁻¹]
25	MU	AnOHM_Ch		Bulk transfer coefficient for this surface to use in AnOHM [-]

SUEWS_Soil.txt

SUEWS_Soil.txt specifies the characteristics of the sub-surface soil below each of the non-water surface types (Paved, Bldgs, EveTr, DecTr, Grass, BSoil). The model does not have a soil store below the water surfaces. Note that these sub-surface soil stores are different to the bare soil/unmanaged surface cover type. Each of the non-water surface types need to link to soil characteristics specified here. If the soil characteristics are assumed to be the same for all surface types, use a single code value to link the characteristics here with the SoilTypeCode columns in [SUEWS_NonVeg.txt](#) and [SUEWS_Veg.txt](#).

Soil moisture can either be provided using observational data in the met forcing file (smd_choice = 1 or 2 in [RunControl.nml](#)) and providing some metadata information here (OBS_ columns), or modelled by SUEWS (smd_choice = 0 in [RunControl.nml](#)). - **Note, the option to use observational data is not operational in the current release!**

No.	Use	Column name	Example	Description
1	L	Code	331	Code linking to the SoilTypeCode column in SUEWS_NonVeg.txt (for Paved, Bldgs and BSoil surfaces) and SUEWS_Veg.txt (for EveTr, DecTr and Grass surfaces).

				Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt.
2	MD	SoilDepth	350	Depth of sub-surface soil store [mm] i.e. the depth of soil beneath the surface
3	MD	SoilStoreCap	150	Capacity of sub-surface soil store [mm] i.e. how much water can be stored in the sub-surface soil when at maximum capacity. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> SoilStoreCap must not be greater than SoilDepth.
4	MD	SatHydraulicCond	0.0005	Hydraulic conductivity for saturated soil [mm s^{-1}]
5	MD	SoilDensity	1.16	Soil density [kg m^{-3}]
6	O	InfiltrationRate	-999	Infiltration rate [mm h^{-1}] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not currently used
7	O	OBS_SMDepth		Depth of soil moisture measurements [mm] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use only if soil moisture is observed and provided in the met forcing file and <code>smd_choice = 1</code> or <code>2</code>. Use of observed soil moisture not currently tested
8	O	OBS_SMCap		Maximum observed soil moisture [$\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$ or kg kg^{-1}] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use only if soil moisture is observed and provided in the met forcing file and <code>smd_choice = 1</code> or <code>2</code>. Use of observed soil moisture not currently tested
9	O	OBS_SoilNotRocks		Fraction of soil without rocks [-] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use only if soil moisture is observed and provided in the met forcing file and <code>smd_choice = 1</code> or <code>2</code>. Use of observed soil moisture not currently tested

SUEWS_Conductance.txt

SUEWS_Conductance.txt contains the parameters needed for the Jarvis (1976) surface conductance model used in the modelling of evaporation in SUEWS. These values should **not** be changed independently of each other. The suggested values below have been derived using datasets for Los Angeles and Vancouver (see Järvi et al. (2011)^[1]) and should be used with **gsModel=1**. An alternative formulation (`gsModel=2`) uses slightly different functional forms and different coefficients (with different units).

No.	Use	Column name	Example	Description
1	L	Code		Code linking to the CondCode column in <u>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</u> . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt.
2	MD	G1	16.4764	Related to maximum surface conductance [mm s^{-1}]
3	MD	G2	566.0923	Related to Kdown dependence [W m^{-2}]
4	MD	G3	0.2163	Related to VPD dependence [units depend on <code>gsChoice</code> in <u>RunControl.nml</u>]
5	MD	G4	3.3649	Related to VPD dependence [units depend on <code>gsChoice</code> in <u>RunControl.nml</u>]
6	MD	G5	11.0764	Related to temperature dependence [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
7	MD	G6	0.0176	Related to soil moisture dependence [mm^{-1}]
8	MD	TH	40	Upper air temperature limit [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
9	MD	TL	0	Lower air temperature limit [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
10	MD	S1	0.45	Related to soil moisture dependence [-] <i>These will change in the future to ensure consistency with soil behaviour</i>

11	MD	S2	15	Related to soil moisture dependence [mm] <i>These will change in the future to ensure consistency with soil behaviour</i>
12	MD	Kmax	1200	Maximum incoming shortwave radiation [W m^{-2}]
13	MD	gsModel	1	Determines which surface conductance parameterisation to use <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 1 = Järvi et al. (2011)^[11] ▪ 2 = Ward et al. (2016)^[21] Recommended. The parameterisation specified here must match the coefficients specified in the other columns of SUEWS_Conductance.txt.

SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeat.txt

SUEWS_AnthropogenicHeatFlux.txt provides the parameters needed to model the anthropogenic heat flux using either the method of Järvi et al. (2011) based on heating and cooling degree days (AnthropHeatMethod = 2 in 4.1 [RunControl.nml](#)) or the method of Loridan et al. (2011) based on air temperature (AnthropHeatMethod = 1 in [RunControl.nml](#)). The sub-daily variation in anthropogenic heat flux is modelled according to the daily cycles specified in SUEWS_Profiles.txt. Alternatively, if available, the anthropogenic heat flux can be provided in the met forcing file (and set AnthropHeatMethod = 0 in [RunControl.nml](#)), in which case all columns here except Code and BaseTHDD should be set to '-999'.

No.	Use	Column name	Example	Description
1	L	Code	331	Code linking to the AnthropogenicCode column in SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt . Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt .
2	MU	BaseTHDD	18.2	Base temperature for heating degree days [$^{\circ}\text{C}$] e.g. Sailor and Vasireddy (2006) ^[39]
3	MU, O	QF_A_Weekday		Base value for QF on weekdays [$\text{W m}^{-2} (\text{Cap ha}^{-1})^{-1}$] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Use with AnthropHeatChoice = 2 Example values [$\text{W m}^{-2} (\text{Cap ha}^{-1})^{-1}$] 0.3081 Järvi et al. (2011) ^[11] 0.1000 Järvi et al. (2014) ^[15]
4	MU, O	QF_B_Weekday		Parameter related to cooling degree days on weekdays [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1} (\text{Cap ha}^{-1})^{-1}$] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Use with AnthropHeatMethod = 2 Example values [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1} (\text{Cap ha}^{-1})^{-1}$] 0.0099 Järvi et al. (2011) ^[11] 0.0099 Järvi et al. (2014) ^[15]
5	MU, O	QF_C_Weekday		Parameter related to heating degree days on weekdays [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1} (\text{Cap ha}^{-1})^{-1}$] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Use with AnthropHeatMethod = 2 Example values [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1} (\text{Cap ha}^{-1})^{-1}$] 0.0102 Järvi et al. (2011) ^[11] 0.0102 Järvi et al. (2014) ^[15]
6	MU, O	QF_A_Weekend		Base value for QF on weekends [$\text{W m}^{-2} (\text{Cap ha}^{-1})^{-1}$] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Use with AnthropHeatMethod = 2 Example values [$\text{W m}^{-2} (\text{Cap ha}^{-1})^{-1}$] 0.3081 Järvi et al. (2011) ^[11]

			0.1000 Järvi et al. (2014) ^[15]
7	MU, O	QF_B_Weekend	0-1 Parameter related to cooling degree days on weekends [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1} (\text{Cap ha}^{-1})^{-1}$] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use with AnthropHeatMethod = 2 Example values [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1} (\text{Cap ha}^{-1})^{-1}$] 0.0099 Järvi et al. (2011) ^[11] 0.0099 Järvi et al. (2014) ^[15]
8	MU, O	QF_C_Weekend	Parameter related to heating degree days on weekends [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1} (\text{Cap ha}^{-1})^{-1}$] Use with AnthropHeatMethod = 2 Example values [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1} (\text{Cap ha}^{-1})^{-1}$] 0.0102 Järvi et al. (2011) ^[11] 0.0102 Järvi et al. (2014) ^[15]
9	MU, O	AHMin	15 Minimum QF [W m^{-2}] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use with AnthropHeatMethod = 1 e.g. Loridan et al. (2011) ^[5]
10	MU, O	AHSlope	2.7 Slope of QF versus air temperature [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use with AnthropHeatMethod = 1 e.g. Loridan et al. (2011) ^[5]
11	MU, O	TCritic	7 Critical temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use with AnthropHeatMethod = 1 e.g. Loridan et al. (2011) ^[5]

SUEWS_Irrigation.txt

SUEWS includes a simple model for external water use if observed data are not available. The model calculates daily water use from the mean daily air temperature, number of days since rain and fraction of irrigated area using automatic/manual irrigation. The sub-daily pattern of water use is modelled according to the daily cycles specified in [SUEWS_Profiles.txt](#).

Alternatively, if available, the external water use can be provided in the met forcing file (and set WaterUseMethod = 1 in [RunControl.nml](#)), in which case all columns here except Code should be set to '-999'.

No.	Use	Column name	Example	Description
1	L	Code		Code linking to [#SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt] for irrigation modelling (IrrigationCode). Value of integer is arbitrary but must match codes specified in SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt .
2	MU	Ie_start	1-366	Day when irrigation starts [DOY]
3	MU	Ie_end	1-366	Day when irrigation ends [DOY]
4	MU	InternalWaterUse	0	Internal water use [mm h^{-1}]
5	MU	Faut	0-1	Fraction of irrigated area that is irrigated using automated systems (e.g. sprinklers).
6	MD	Ie_a1	-84.54	Coefficient for automatic irrigation model [mm d^{-1}]
7	MD	Ie_a2	9.96	Coefficient for automatic irrigation model [$\text{mm d}^{-1} \text{ } ^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$]
8	MD	Ie_a3	3.67	Coefficient for automatic irrigation model [mm d^{-2}]
9	MD	Ie_m1	-25.36	Coefficient for manual irrigation model [mm d^{-1}]
10	MD	Ie_m2	3.00	Coefficient for manual irrigation model [$\text{mm d}^{-1} \text{ } ^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$]

11	MD	Ie_m3	1.10	Coefficient for manual irrigation model [mm d ⁻²]
12	MU	DayWat(1)	0 or 1	Irrigation allowed on Sundays [1], if not [0]
13	MU	DayWat(2)	0 or 1	Irrigation allowed on Mondays [1], if not [0]
14	MU	DayWat(3)	0 or 1	Irrigation allowed on Tuesdays [1], if not [0]
15	MU	DayWat(4)	0 or 1	Irrigation allowed on Wednesdays [1], if not [0]
16	MU	DayWat(5)	0 or 1	Irrigation allowed on Thursdays [1], if not [0]
17	MU	DayWat(6)	0 or 1	Irrigation allowed on Fridays [1], if not [0]
18	MU	DayWat(7)	0 or 1	Irrigation allowed on Saturdays [1], if not [0]
19	MU	DayWatPer(1)	0-1	Fraction of properties using irrigation on Sundays [0-1]
20	MU	DayWatPer(2)	0-1	Fraction of properties using irrigation on Mondays [0-1]
21	MU	DayWatPer(3)	0-1	Fraction of properties using irrigation on Tuesdays [0-1]
22	MU	DayWatPer(4)	0-1	Fraction of properties using irrigation on Wednesdays [0-1]
23	MU	DayWatPer(5)	0-1	Fraction of properties using irrigation on Thursdays [0-1]
24	MU	DayWatPer(6)	0-1	Fraction of properties using irrigation on Fridays [0-1]
25	MU	DayWatPer(7)	0-1	Fraction of properties using irrigation on Saturdays [0-1]

SUEWS_Profiles.txt

SUEWS_Profiles.txt specifies the daily cycle of variables related to human behaviour (energy use, water use and snow clearing). Different profiles can be specified for weekdays and weekends. The profiles are provided at hourly resolution here; the model will then interpolate the hourly energy and water use profiles to the resolution of the model time step and normalize the values provided. Thus it does not matter whether columns 2-25 add up to, say 1, 24, or another number, because the model will handle this. Currently, the snow clearing profiles are not interpolated as these are effectively a switch (0 or 1).

If the anthropogenic heat flux and water use are specified in the met forcing file, the energy and water use profiles are not used.

Profiles are specified for the following

- Anthropogenic heat flux (weekday and weekend)
- Water use (weekday and weekend; manual and automatic irrigation)
- Snow removal (weekday and weekend)
- Human activity (weekday and weekend) - **not used in v2017a**.

No.	Use	Column name	Example	Description
1	L	Code		Code linking to the following columns in <u>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</u> : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ EnergyUseProfWD : Anthropogenic heat flux, weekdays ▪ EnergyUseProfWE : Anthropogenic heat flux, weekends ▪ WaterUseProfManuWD : Manual irrigation, weekdays ▪ WaterUseProfManuWE : Manual irrigation, weekends ▪ WaterUseProfAutoWD : Automatic irrigation, weekdays ▪ WaterUseProfAutoWE : Automatic irrigation, weekends ▪ SnowClearingProfWD : Snow clearing, weekdays ▪ SnowClearingProfWE : Snow clearing, weekends ▪ ActivityProfWD : Human activity, weekdays ▪ ActivityProfWE : Human activity, weekends ▪ Value of integer is arbitrary but must match codes specified in SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt.
2-25	MU	0-23		Multiplier for each hour of the day [-] for energy and water use.

			For SnowClearing, set those hours to 1 when snow removal from paved and roof surface is allowed (0 otherwise) if the snow removal limits set in the SUEWS_NonVeg.txt (SnowLimRemove column) are exceeded.
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SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt

SUEWS_WithinGridWaterDist.txt specifies the movement of water between surfaces within a grid/area. It allows impervious connectivity to be taken into account.

Each row corresponds to a surface type (linked by the Code in column 1 to the [SiteSelect.txt](#) columns: WithinGridPavedCode, WithinGridBldgsCode, ..., WithinGridWaterCode). Each column contains the fraction of water flowing from the surface type to each of the other surface types or to runoff or the sub-surface soil store.

Note:

- The sum of each row (excluding the Code) must equal 1.
- Water cannot flow from one surface to that same surface, so the diagonal elements should be zero.
- The row corresponding to the water surface should be zero, as there is currently no flow permitted from the water surface to other surfaces by the model.
- Currently water **cannot** go to both runoff and soil store (i.e. it must go to one or the other – runoff for impervious surfaces; soilstore for pervious surfaces).

In the table below, for example,

- all flow from paved surfaces goes to runoff;
- 90% of flow from buildings goes to runoff, with small amounts going to other surfaces (mostly paved surfaces as buildings are often surrounded by paved areas);
- all flow from vegetated and bare soil areas goes into the sub-surface soil store;
- the row corresponding to water contains zeros (as it is currently not used).

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10		
Code	ToPaved	ToBuilt	ToEveTr	ToDecTr	ToGrass	ToBSoil	ToWater	ToRunoff	ToSoilStore			
10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	!	Paved	
20	0.06	0	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0	0.9	0	!	Bldgs	
30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	!	EveTr	
40	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	!	DecTr	
50	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	!	Grass	
60	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	!	BSoil	
70	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	!	Water	

SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt

OHM, the Objective Hysteresis Model (Grimmond et al. 1991)^[9] calculates the storage heat flux as a function of net all-wave radiation and surface characteristics.

- For each surface, OHM requires three model coefficients (a1, a2, a3). The three should be selected as a set.
- The **SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt** file provides these coefficients for each surface type.
- A variety of values has been derived for different materials and can be found in the literature (see: [Typical Values](#)).
- Coefficients can be changed depending on:
 1. surface wetness state (wet/dry) based on the calculated surface wetness state and soil moisture.
 2. season (summer/winter) based on a 5-day running mean air temperature.
- To use the same coefficients irrespective of wet/dry and summer/winter conditions, use the same code for all four OHM columns (OHMCode_SummerWet, OHMCode_SummerDry, OHMCode_WinterWet and OHMCode_WinterDry).

Note, **AnOHM** does not use the coefficients specified in SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt but instead requires three parameters to be specified for each surface type (including snow): heat capacity, thermal conductivity and bulk transfer coefficient. These are specified in [SUEWS_NonVeg.txt](#), [SUEWS_Veg.txt](#), [SUEWS_Water.txt](#) and [SUEWS_Snow.txt](#). No additional files are required for AnOHM.

Note AnOHM is under development in v2017a and should not be used!

No.	Use	Column name	Example	Description
1	L	Code	331	Code linking to the OHMCode_SummerWet, OHMCode_SummerDry, OHMCode_WinterWet and OHMCode_WinterDry columns in SUEWS_NonVeg.txt, SUEWS_Veg.txt, SUEWS_Water.txt and SUEWS_Snow.txt files. Value of integer is arbitrary but must match code specified in SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt.
2	MU	a1		Coefficient for Q* term [-]
3	MU	a2		Coefficient for dQ*/dt term [h]
4	MU	a3		Constant term [W m ⁻²]

SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt

Note ESTM is under development in v2017a and should not be used!

The Element Surface Temperature Method (ESTM) (Offerle et al., 2005) calculates the net storage heat flux from surface temperatures. In the method the three-dimensional urban volume is reduced to four 1-d elements (i.e. building roofs, walls, and internal mass and ground (road, vegetation, etc)). The storage heat flux is calculated from the heat conduction through the different elements. For the inside surfaces of the roof and walls, and both surfaces for the internal mass (ceilings/floors, internal walls), the surface temperature of the element is determined by setting the conductive heat transfer out of (in to) the surface equal to the radiative and convective heat losses (gains). Each element (roof, wall, internal element and ground) can have maximum five layers and each layer has three parameters tied to it: thickness (x), thermal conductivity (k), volumetric heat capacity (rhoCp).

If ESTM is used (QSchoice=4), the files SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt, ESTMinput.nml and SS YYYY ESTM Ts data tt.txt should be prepared.

SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt contains the parameters for the layers of each of the elements (roofs, wall, ground, internal mass).

- If less than five layers are used, the parameters for unused layers should be set to -999.
- The ESTM coefficients with the prefix *Surf_* must be specified for each surface type (plus snow) but the *Wall_* and *Internal_* variables apply to the building surfaces only.
- For each grid, one set of ESTM coefficients must be specified for each surface type; for paved and building surfaces it is possible to specify up to three and five sets of coefficients per grid (e.g. to represent different building materials) using the relevant columns in SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt. For the model to use these columns in site select, the ESTMCode column in SUEWS_NonVeg.txt should be set to zero.

No.	Use	Column name	Example	Description
1	L	Code	331	Code linking to the ESTMCode column in SUEWS_NonVeg.txt, SUEWS_Veg.txt, SUEWS_Water.txt and SUEWS_Snow.txt files. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ For buildings and paved surfaces, set to zero if there is more than one ESTM class per grid and the codes and surface fractions specified in <u>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</u> will be used instead.
2	MU	Surf_thick1	0.2	Thickness of the first layer [m] for roofs (building surfaces) and ground (all other surfaces)
3	MU	Surf_k1	0.5	Thermal conductivity of the first layer [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
4	MU	Surf_rhoCp1	840000	Volumetric heat capacity of the first layer [J m ⁻³ K ⁻¹]
5	O	Surf_thick2	-	Thickness of the second layer [m] (if no second layer, set to -999.)
6	O	Surf_k2	-	Thermal conductivity of the second layer [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
7	O	Surf_rhoCp2	-	Volumetric heat capacity of the second layer [J m ⁻³ K ⁻¹]

8	O	Surf_thick3	-	Thickness of the third layer [m] (if no third layer, set to -999.)
9	O	Surf_k3	-	Thermal conductivity of the third layer[W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
10	O	Surf_rhoCp3	-	Volumetric heat capacity of the third layer[J m ⁻³ K ⁻¹]
11	O	Surf_thick4	-	Thickness of the fourth layer [m] (if no fourth layer, set to -999.)
12	O	Surf_k4	-	Thermal conductivity of the fourth layer[W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
13	O	Surf_rhoCp4	-	Volumetric heat capacity of the fourth layer [J m ⁻³ K ⁻¹]
14	O	Surf_thick5	-	Thickness of the fifth layer [m] (if no fifth layer, set to -999.)
15	O	Surf_k5	-	Thermal conductivity of the fifth layer [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
16	O	Surf_rhoCp5	-	Volumetric heat capacity of the fifth layer [J m ⁻³ K ⁻¹]
17	MU	Wall_thick1	-	Thickness of the first layer [m] for building surfaces only; set to -999 for all other surfaces
18	MU	Wall_k1	-	Thermal conductivity of the first layer [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
19	MU	Wall_rhoCp1	-	Volumetric heat capacity of the first layer [J m ⁻³ K ⁻¹]
20	O	Wall_thick2	-	Thickness of the second layer [m] (if no second layer, set to -999.)
21	O	Wall_k2	-	Thermal conductivity of the second layer [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
22	O	Wall_rhoCp2	-	Volumetric heat capacity of the second layer [J m ⁻³ K ⁻¹]
23	O	Wall_thick3	-	Thickness of the third layer [m] (if no third layer, set to -999.)
24	O	Wall_k3	-	Thermal conductivity of the third layer [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
25	O	Wall_rhoCp3	-	Volumetric heat capacity of the third layer [J m ⁻³ K ⁻¹]
26	O	Wall_thick4	-	Thickness of the fourth layer [m] (if no fourth layer, set to -999.)
27	O	Wall_k4	-	Thermal conductivity of the fourth layer[W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
28	O	Wall_rhoCp4	-	Volumetric heat capacity of the fourth layer [J m ⁻³ K ⁻¹]
29	O	Wall_thick5	-	Thickness of the fifth layer [m] (if no fifth layer, set to -999.)
30	O	Wall_k5	-	Thermal conductivity of the fifth layer[W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
31	O	Wall_rhoCp5	-	Volumetric heat capacity of the fifth layer [J m ⁻³ K ⁻¹]
32	MU	Internal_thick1	-	Thickness of the first layer [m] for building surfaces only; set to -999 for all other surfaces
33	MU	Internal_k1	-	Thermal conductivity of the first layer [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
34	MU	Internal_rhoCp1	-	Volumetric heat capacity of the first layer[J m ⁻³ K ⁻¹]
35	O	Internal_thick2	-	Thickness of the second layer [m] (if no second layer, set to -999.)
36	O	Internal_k2	-	Thermal conductivity of the second layer [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
37	O	Internal_rhoCp2	-	Volumetric heat capacity of the second layer [J m ⁻³ K ⁻¹]
38	O	Internal_thick3	-	Thickness of the third layer [m] (if no third layer, set to -999.)
39	O	Internal_k3	-	Thermal conductivity of the third layer [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
40	O	Internal_rhoCp3	-	Volumetric heat capacity of the third layer[J m ⁻³ K ⁻¹]
41	O	Internal_thick4	-	Thickness of the fourth layer [m] (if no fourth layer, set to -999.)
42	O	Internal_k4	-	Thermal conductivity of the fourth layer [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
43	O	Internal_rhoCp4	-	Volumetric heat capacity of the fourth layer [J m ⁻³ K ⁻¹]

44	O	Internal_thick5	-	Thickness of the fifth layer [m] (if no fifth layer, set to -999.)
45	O	Internal_k5	-	Thermal conductivity of the fifth layer [$\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]
46	O	Internal_rhoCp5	-	Volumetric heat capacity of the fifth layer [$\text{J m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$]
47	MU	nroom	-	Number of rooms per floor for building surfaces only
48	MU	Internal_albedo	-	Albedo of all internal elements for building surfaces only
49	MU	Internal_emissivity	-	Emissivity of all internal elements for building surfaces only
50	O	Internal_CHwall		Bulk transfer coefficient of internal wall [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$] (for building surfaces only and if IblldCHmod == 0 in ESTMinput.nml)
51	O	Internal_CHroof		Bulk transfer coefficient of internal roof [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$] (for building surfaces only and if IblldCHmod == 0 in ESTMinput.nml)
52	O	Internal_CHbld		Bulk transfer coefficient of internal building elements [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$] (for building surfaces only and if IblldCHmod == 0 in ESTMinput.nml)

Additional ESTM-related files

Depending on how the storage heat flux is calculated (specified by StorageHeatMethod in [RunControl.nml](#)), different input files are required:

Option	StorageHeatMethod	Files needed
<i>OHM</i>	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Coefficients a1, a2, a3 specified in SUEWS_OHMCoefficients.txt
<i>Observations</i>	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Storage heat flux is provide in meteorological forcing file
<i>AnOHM</i>	3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Thermal properties specified with other site characteristics in SUEWS_NonVeg.txt, SUEWS_Veg.txt, SUEWS_Water.txt and SUEWS_Snow.txt
<i>ESTM</i>	4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Properties of each element specified in SUEWS_ESTMCoefficients.txt ▪ Model options specified in ESTMinput.nml ▪ Time-series of surface temperatures provided in SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt

Note ESTM is under development in v2017a and should not be used!

The following input files are required if ESTM is used to calculate the storage heat flux.

ESTMinput.nml

ESTMinput.nml specifies the model settings and default values.

- The file contents can be in any order.

Name	Description
<i>TsurfChoice</i>	Source of surface temperature data used.
0	*Tsurf in SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt used for all surface elements.
1	*Tground, Troof and Twall in SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt used. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Input surface temperature are different for ground, roof and wall.
2	*Tground, Troof, Twall_n, Twall_e, Twall_s and Twall_w in SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt used. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Wall surface temperature is different for four directions.
<i>evolveTibld</i>	Source of internal building temperature (Tibld)
0	*Tiair in SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt used.
1	*Tibld calculated considering the effect of anthropogenic heat from HVAC

	2	*Tibld calculated without considering the influence of HVAC.
<i>IbldCHmod</i>	Method to calculate internal convective heat exchange coefficients (CH) for internal building, wall and roof if evolveTibld is 1 or 2.	
	0	CHs are read from SUEWS_ESTMcoefficients.txt.
	1	CHs are calculated based on ASHRAE (2001)
	2	CHs are calculated based on Awbi (1998).
<i>LBC_soil</i>	Soil temperature at lowest boundary condition [°C]	
<i>Theat_on</i>	Temperature at which heat control is turned on (used when evolveTibld =1) [°C]	
<i>Theat_off</i>	Temperature at which heat control is turned off (used when evolveTibld=1) [°C]	
<i>Theat_fix</i>	Ideal internal building temperature [°C]	

SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt

SSss_YYYY_ESTM_Ts_data_tt.txt contains a time-series of input surface temperature for roof, wall, ground and internal elements.

No.	Column name	Description
1	iy	Year [YYYY]
2	id	Day of year [DOY]
3	it	Hour [H]
4	imin	Minute [M]
5	Tiair	Indoor air temperature [°C]
6	Tsurf	Bulk surface temperature [°C] (used when TsurfCoice = 0)
7	Troof	Roof surface temperature [°C] (used when TsurfChoice = 1 or 2)
8	Troad	Ground surface temperature [°C] (used when TsurfChoice = 1 or 2)
9	Twall	Wall surface temperature [°C] (used when TsurfChoice = 1)
10	Twall_n	North-facing wall surface temperature [°C] (used when TsurfChoice = 2)
11	Twall_e	East-facing wall surface temperature [°C] (used when TsurfChoice = 2)
12	Twall_s	South-facing wall surface temperature [°C] (used when TsurfChoice = 2)
13	Twall_w	West-facing wall surface temperature [°C] (used when TsurfChoice = 2)

Initial Conditions file

To start the model, information about the conditions at the start of the run is required. This information is provided in initial conditions file. One file can be specified for each grid (MultipleInitFiles=1 in [RunControl.nml](#), filename includes grid number) or, alternatively, a single file can be specified for all grids (MultipleInitFiles=0 in [RunControl.nml](#), no grid number in the filename). After that, a new InitialConditionsSSss_YYYY.nml file will be written for each grid for the following years. It is recommended that you look at these files (written to the input directory) to check the status of various surfaces at the end or the run. This may help you get more realistic starting values if you are uncertain what they should be. Note this file will be created for each year for multiyear runs for each grid. If the run finishes before the end of the year the InitialConditions file is still written and the file name is appended with '_EndofRun'.

The two most important pieces of information in the initial conditions file is the soil moisture and state of vegetation at the start of the run. This is the minimal information required; other information can be provided if known, otherwise SUEWS will make an estimate of initial conditions.

InitialConditionsSSss_YYYY.nml

- Variables can be in any order

Parameters	Required/Optional	Unit	Comments
Soil moisture states			
<i>SoilstorePavedState</i>	R	mm	Initial state of the soil water storage under paved surfaces.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For maximum values, see the used soil code in SUEWS_Soil.txt
<i>SoilstoreBldgsState</i>	R	mm	Initial state of the soil water storage under buildings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> For maximum values, see the used soil code in SUEWS_Soil.txt
<i>SoilstoreEveTrState</i>	R	mm	Initial state of the soil water storage under evergreen trees <ul style="list-style-type: none"> For maximum values, see the used soil code in SUEWS_Soil.txt
<i>SoilstoreDecTrState</i>	R	mm	Initial state of the soil water storage under deciduous trees <ul style="list-style-type: none"> For maximum values, see the used soil code in SUEWS_Soil.txt
<i>SoilstoreGrassState</i>	R	mm	Initial state of the soil water storage under grass <ul style="list-style-type: none"> For maximum values, see the used soil code in SUEWS_Soil.txt
<i>SoilstoreBSoilState</i>	R	mm	Initial state of the soil water storage under bare soil surfaces <ul style="list-style-type: none"> For maximum values, see the used soil code in SUEWS_Soil.txt
			(Note: no soil store below water surface)
Vegetation parameters			Can be set individually or using a single vegetation parameter (LeavesOutInitially)
<i>LeavesOutInitially</i>	(O)	-	Sets all required vegetation parameters accordingly using information for full leaf-out (1)/complete leaf-off (0) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> If the model run starts in winter when trees are bare, set <i>LeavesOutInitially</i> = 0 and the vegetation parameters will be set accordingly based on the values set in SUEWS_SiteInfo.xlsm. If the model run starts in summer when leaves are fully out, set <i>LeavesOutInitially</i> = 1 and the vegetation parameters will be set accordingly based on the values set in SUEWS_SiteInfo.xlsm. Not <i>LeavesOutInitially</i> can only be set to 0, 1 or -999 (fractional values cannot be used to indicate partial leaf-out). The value of <i>LeavesOutInitially</i> overrides any values provided for the individual vegetation parameters. To prevent <i>LeavesOutInitially</i> from setting the initial conditions, either omit it from the namelist or set to -999. If values are provided individually, they should be consistent the information provided in SUEWS_Veg.txt and the time of year. If values are provided individually, values for all required surfaces must be provided (i.e. specifying only <i>albGrass0</i> but not <i>albDecTr0</i> nor <i>albEveTr0</i> is not permitted).
<i>GDD_1_0</i>	O	°C	Growing degree days for leaf growth.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cannot be negative. If leaves are already full, then this should be the same as GDDFull in SUEWS_Veg.txt. If <i>winter</i>, set to 0. It is important that the vegetation characteristics are set correctly (i.e. for the start of the run in summer/winter).
<i>GDD_2_0</i>	O	°C	<p>Growing degree days for senescence growth.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cannot be positive If the leaves are full but in early/mid summer then set to 0. If <i>late summer or autumn</i>, this should be a negative value. If <i>leaves are off</i>, then use the values of SDDFull in SUEWS_Veg.txt to guide your minimum value. It is important that the vegetation characteristics are set correctly (i.e. for the start of the run in summer/winter).
<i>LAIinitialEveTr</i>	O	m ⁻² m ⁻²	Initial LAI for evergreen trees. The recommended values can be found from SUEWS_Veg.txt
<i>LAIinitialDecTr</i>	O	m ⁻² m ⁻²	Initial LAI for deciduous trees. The recommended values can be found from SUEWS_Veg.txt
<i>LAIinitialGrass</i>	O	m ⁻² m ⁻²	Initial LAI for irrigated grass. The recommended values can be found from SUEWS_Veg.txt
<i>albEveTr0</i>	O	-	Albedo of evergreen surface on day 0 of run
<i>albDecTr0</i>	O	-	Albedo of deciduous surface on day 0 of run
<i>albGrass0</i>	O	-	Albedo of grass surface on day 0 of run
<i>decidCap0</i>	O	mm	Deciduous storage capacity on day 0 of run.
<i>porosity0</i>	O	-	Porosity of deciduous vegetation on day 0 of run. This varies between 0.2 (leaf-on) and 0.6 (leaf-off).
Recent meteorology			
<i>DaysSinceRain</i>	O	days	<p>Number of days since rainfall occurred.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Important to use correct value if starting in summer season If starting when external water use is not occurring it will be reset with the first rain so can just be set to 0. If unknown, SUEWS sets to zero by default. Used to model irrigation.
<i>Temp_CO</i>	O	°C	<p>Daily mean temperature [°C] for the day before the run starts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> If unknown, SUEWS uses the mean temperature for the first day of the run. Used to model irrigation and anthropogenic heat flux.
Above Ground State			
<i>PavedState</i>	O		Initial wetness state of paved surface (0 indicates dry, wet otherwise).

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> If unknown, model assumes dry surfaces (acceptable as rainfall or irrigation will update these states quickly).
<i>BldgsState</i>	O	mm	<p>Initial wetness state for buildings (0 indicates dry, wet otherwise).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> If unknown, model assumes dry surfaces (acceptable as rainfall or irrigation will update these states quickly).
<i>EveTrState</i>	O	mm	<p>Initial wetness state of evergreen trees (0 indicates dry, wet otherwise).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> If unknown, model assumes dry surfaces (acceptable as rainfall or irrigation will update these states quickly).
<i>DecTrState</i>	O	mm	<p>Initial wetness state of deciduous trees (0 indicates dry, wet otherwise).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> If unknown, model assumes dry surfaces (acceptable as rainfall or irrigation will update these states quickly).
<i>GrassState</i>	O	mm	<p>Initial wetness state of grass (0 indicates dry, wet otherwise).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> If unknown, model assumes dry surfaces (acceptable as rainfall or irrigation will update these states quickly).
<i>BSoilState</i>	O	mm	<p>Initial wetness state of bare soil surface (0 indicates dry, wet otherwise).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> If unknown, model assumes dry surfaces (acceptable as rainfall or irrigation will update these states quickly).
<i>WaterState</i>	O	mm	<p>Initial state of water surface (must be set > 0, as 0 indicates dry surface).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> For a large water body (e.g. river, sea, lake) set <i>WaterState</i> to a large value, e.g. 20000 mm; for small water bodies (e.g. ponds, fountains) set <i>WaterState</i> to smaller value, e.g. 1000 mm. This value must not exceed StateLimit specified in <u>SUEWS_Water.txt</u>. If unknown, model uses value of WaterDepth specified in <u>SUEWS_Water.txt</u>.
<i>Snow-related parameters</i>			Can be set individually or using a single snow parameter (<i>SnowInitially</i>)
<i>SnowInitially</i>	(O)	-	<p>Sets all required snow-related parameters accordingly if there is initially no snow</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> If the model run starts when there is no snow on the ground, set <i>SnowInitially</i> = 0 and the snow-related parameters will be set accordingly. If the model run starts when there is snow on the ground, the following snow-related parameters must be set appropriately. The value of <i>SnowInitially</i> overrides any values provided for the individual snow-related parameters.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ To prevent SnowInitially from setting the initial conditions, either omit it from the namelist or set to -999. ▪ If values are provided individually, they should be consistent the information provided in <u>SUEWS_Snow.txt</u>.
<i>SnowWaterPavedState</i>	O	mm	Initial amount of liquid water in the snow on paved surfaces.
<i>SnowWaterBldgsState</i>	O	mm	Initial amount of liquid water in the snow on buildings
<i>SnowWaterEveTrState</i>	O	mm	Initial amount of liquid water in the snow on evergreen trees
<i>SnowWaterDecTrState</i>	O	mm	Initial amount of liquid water in the snow on deciduous trees
<i>SnowWaterGrassState</i>	O	mm	Initial amount of liquid water in the snow on grass surfaces
<i>SnowWaterBSoilState</i>	O	mm	Initial amount of liquid water in the snow on bare soil surfaces
<i>SnowWaterWaterState</i>	O	mm	Initial amount of liquid water in the snow in water
<i>SnowPackPaved</i>	O	mm	Initial snow water equivalent if the snow on paved surfaces
<i>SnowPackBldgs</i>	O	mm	Initial snow water equivalent if the snow on buildings
<i>SnowPackEveTr</i>	O	mm	Initial snow water equivalent if the snow on evergreen trees
<i>SnowPackDecTr</i>	O	mm	Initial snow water equivalent if the snow on deciduous trees
<i>SnowPackGrass</i>	O	mm	Initial snow water equivalent if the snow on grass surfaces
<i>SnowPackBSoil</i>	O	mm	Initial snow water equivalent if the snow on bare soil surfaces
<i>SnowPackWater</i>	O	mm	Initial snow water equivalent if the snow on water
<i>SnowFracPaved</i>	O	-	Initial plan area fraction of snow on paved surfaces
<i>SnowFracBldgs</i>	O	-	Initial plan area fraction of snow on buildings
<i>SnowFracEveTr</i>	O	-	Initial plan area fraction of snow on evergreen trees
<i>SnowFracDecTr</i>	O	-	Initial plan area fraction of snow on deciduous trees
<i>SnowFracGras</i>	O	-	Initial plan area fraction of snow on grass surfaces
<i>SnowFracBSoil</i>	O	-	Initial plan area fraction of snow on bare soil surfaces
<i>SnowFracWater</i>	O	-	Initial plan area fraction of snow on water
<i>SnowDensPaved</i>	O	kg m ⁻³	Initial snow density on paved surfaces
<i>SnowDensBldgs</i>	O	kg m ⁻³	Initial snow density on buildings
<i>SnowDensEveTr</i>	O	kg m ⁻³	Initial snow density on evergreen trees
<i>SnowDensDecTr</i>	O	kg m ⁻³	Initial snow density on deciduous trees
<i>SnowDensGrass</i>	O	kg m ⁻³	Initial snow density on grass surfaces

<i>SnowDensSoil</i>	O	kg m ⁻³	Initial snow density on bare soil surfaces
<i>SnowDensWater</i>	O	kg m ⁻³	Initial snow density on water

Meteorological input file

SUEWS is designed to run using commonly measured meteorological variables.

- Required inputs must be continuous – i.e. **gap fill** any missing data.
- The table below gives the required (R) and optional (O) additional input variables.
- If an optional input variable is not available or will not be used by the model, enter ‘-999.0’ for this column.
- Since v2017a forcing files no longer need to end with two rows containing ‘-9’ in the first column.
- One single meteorological file can be used for all grids (**MultipleMetFiles=0** in RunControl.nml, no grid number in file name) if appropriate for the study area, or
- separate met files can be used for each grid if data are available (**MultipleMetFiles=1** in RunControl.nml, filename includes grid number).
- The meteorological forcing file names should be appended with the temporal resolution in minutes (SS_YYYY_data_tt.txt, or SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt for multiple grids).
- Separate met forcing files should be provided for each year.
- Files do not need to start/end at the start/end of the year, but they must contain a whole number of days.
- The meteorological input file should match the information given in SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt.
- If a *partial year* is used that specific year must be given in SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt.
- If *multiple years* are used, all years should be included in SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt.
- If a *whole year* (e.g. 2011) is intended to be modelled using an hourly resolution dataset, the number of lines in the met data file should be 8760 and begin and end with:

```

iy      id      it      imin
2011    1        1        0 ...
...
2012    1        0        0 ...
    
```

SSss_YYYY_data_tt.txt

Main meteorological data file.

No.	Use	Column name	Description
1	R	iy	Year [YYYY]
2	R	id	Day of year [DOY]
3	R	it	Hour [H]
4	R	imin	Minute [M]
5	O	qn	Net all-wave radiation [W m ⁻²] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Required if NetRadiationMethod = 1.
6	O	qh	Sensible heat flux [W m ⁻²]
7	O	qe	Latent heat flux [W m ⁻²]
8	O	qs	Storage heat flux [W m ⁻²]
9	O	qf	Anthropogenic heat flux [W m ⁻²]
10	R	U	Wind speed [m s ⁻¹] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Height of the wind speed measurement (z) is needed in <u>SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt</u>.
11	R	RH	Relative Humidity [%]

12	R	Tair	Air temperature [°C]
13	R	pres	Barometric pressure [kPa]
14	R	rain	Rainfall [mm]
15	R	kdown	Incoming shortwave radiation [$W m^{-2}$] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Must be $> 0 W m^{-2}$.
16	O	snow	Snow [mm] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Required if SnowUse = 1
17	O	ldown	Incoming longwave radiation [$W m^{-2}$]
18	O	fclد	Cloud fraction [tenths]
19	O	Wuh	External water use [3]
20	O	xsmd	Observed soil moisture [$^3 m^{-3}$ or $kg kg^{-1}$]
21	O	lai	Observed leaf area index [$m^2 m^{-2}$]
22	O	kdiff	Diffuse radiation [$W m^{-2}$] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recommended if SOLWEIGUse = 1
23	O	kdir	Direct radiation [$W m^{-2}$] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recommended if SOLWEIGUse = 1
24	O	wdir	Wind direction [°] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Currently not implemented

CBL input files

Main references for this part of the model: Onomura et al. (2015)^[17] and Cleugh and Grimmond (2001)^[6].

If CBL slab model is used (CBLuse=1 in RunControl.nml) the following files are needed:

Filename	Purpose
<i>CBL_initial_data.txt</i>	Gives initial data every morning when CBL slab model starts running. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> filename must match the InitialData_FileName in CBLInput.nml. fixed format.
<i>CBLInput.nml</i>	Specifies run options, parameters and input file names. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can be in any order

CBL_initial_data.txt

This file should give initial data every morning when CBL slab model starts running. The file name should match the InitialData_FileName in CBLInput.nml.

Definitions and example file of initial values prepared for Sacramento.

No.	Column name	Description
1	id	Day of year [DOY]
2	zi0	initial convective boundary layer height (m)
3	gamt_Km	vertical gradient of potential temperature ($K m^{-1}$) strength of the inversion
4	gamq_gkgm	vertical gradient of specific humidity ($g kg^{-1} m^{-1}$)
5	Theta+_K	potential temperature at the top of CBL (K)
6	q+_gkg	specific humidity at the top of CBL ($g kg^{-1}$)
7	Theta_K	potential temperature in CBL (K)
8	q_gkg	specific humidity in CBL ($g kg^{-1}$)

- gamt_Km and gamq_gkgm written to two significant figures are required for the model performance in appropriate ranges^[17].

<i>id</i>	<i>zi0</i>	<i>gamt_Km</i>	<i>gamq_gkgm</i>	<i>Theta+_K</i>	<i>q+_gkg</i>	<i>theta_K</i>	<i>q_gkg</i>
234	188	0.032	0.00082	290.4	9.6	288.7	8.3

235	197	0.089	0.089	290.2	8.4	288.3	8.7
/	:	:	:	:	:	:	:
/	:	:	:	:	:	:	:

CBL_Input.nml

Name	Description
EntrainmentType	Determines entrainment scheme. See Cleugh and Grimmond 2000^[16] for details.
	Value Comments
	1 Tennekes and Driedonks (1981) - Recommended
	2 McNaughton and Springs (1986)
	3 Rayner and Watson (1991)
	4 Tennekes (1973)
QH_Choice	Determines QH used for CBL model.
	Value Comments
	1 QH modelled by SUEWS
	2 QH modelled by LUMPS
	3 Observed QH values are used from the meteorological input file
Wsb	Subsidence velocity (m s⁻¹) in eq. 1 and 2 of Onomura et al. (2015)^[17]. (-0.01 m s⁻¹ recommended)
CBLday(id)	CBL model is used for the days you choose. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Set CBLday(id) = 1 ▪ If CBL model is set to run for DOY 175–177, CBLday(175) = 1, CBLday(176) = 1, CBLday(177) = 1
CO2_included	Set to zero in current version
InitialData_use	Determines initial values (see CBL_Initial_data.txt)
	Value Comments
	0 All initial values are calculated. (Not available in current release.)
	1 Take zi0, gamt_Km and gamq_gkgm from input data file. Theta+_K, q+_gkg, Theta_K and q_gkg are calculated using Temp_C, avrh and Pres_kPa in meteorological input file.
	2 Take all initial values from input data file (see CBL_Initial_data.txt).
InitialDataFileName	If InitialData_use ≥ 1, write the file name including the path from site directory e.g. InitialDataFileName='CBLinputfiles\CBL_initial_data.txt'
Sondeflag	Value Comments
	0 Does not read radiosonde vertical profile data - recommended
	1 Reads radiosonde vertical profile data
FileSonde(id)	If Sondeflag=1, write the file name including the path from site directory e.g. FileSonde(id)= 'CBLinputfiles\XXX.txt', XXX is an arbitrary name.

SOLWEIG input files

If the SOLWEIG model option is used (SOLWEIGout=1), spatial data and a SOLWEIGInput.nml file need to be prepared. The Digital Surface Models (DSMs) as well as derivatives originating from DSMs, e.g. Sky View Factors (SVF) must have the same spatial resolution and extent. Since SOLWEIG is a 2D model it will considerably increase computation time and should be used with care.

Description of choices in SOLWEIGinput_file.nml file. The file can be in any order.

Name	Units	Description
------	-------	-------------

<i>Posture</i>	-	Determines the posture of a human for which the radiant fluxes should be considered	
	1	Standing (default)	
	2	Sitting	
<i>absL</i>	-	Absorption coefficient of longwave radiation of a person. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recommended value: 0.97 	
<i>absK</i>	-	Absorption coefficient of shortwave radiation of a person. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recommended value: 0.70 	
<i>heightgravity</i>	m	Centre of gravity for a person. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recommended value for a standing man: 1.1 m 	
<i>usevegdem</i>	-	Vegetation scheme	
	1	Vegetation scheme is active (Lindberg and Grimmond 2011 ^[19])	
	2	No vegetation scheme used	
<i>DSMPath</i>	-	Path to Digital Surface Models (DSM).	
<i>DSMname</i>	-	Ground and Building DSM	
<i>CDSMname</i>	-	Vegetation canopy DSM	
<i>TDSMname</i>	-	Vegetation trunk zone DSM	
<i>TransMin</i>	-	Tranmissivity of K through deciduous vegetation (leaf on) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recommended value: 0.02 (Konarska et al. 2014^[40]) 	
<i>TransMax</i>	-	Tranmissivity of K through deciduous vegetation (leaf off) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recommended value: 0.50 (Konarska et al. 2014^[40]) 	
<i>SVFPath</i>	-	Path to SVFs matrices (See Lindberg and Grimmond (2011) ^[19] for details)	
<i>SVFSuffix</i>	-	Suffix used (if any)	
<i>BuildingName</i>	-	Boolean matrix for locations of building pixels	
<i>row</i>	-	X coordinate for point of interest. Here all variables from the model will written to SOLWEIGpoiOUT.txt	
<i>col</i>	-	Y coordinate for point of interest. Here all variables from the model will written to SOLWEIGpoiOUT.txt	
<i>onlyglobal</i>	-	Global radiation	
	0	Diffuse and direct shortwave radiation taken from met forcing file.	
	1	Diffuse and direct shortwave radiation calculated from Reindl et al. (1990) ^[41]	
<i>SOLWEIGpoi_out</i>	-	Write output variables at point of interest (see below)	
	0	No POI output	
<i>Tmrt_out</i>	-	0	No grid output
	1	Write grid to file (saves as ERSI Ascii grid)	
<i>Lup2d_out</i>	-	0	No grid output
	1	Write grid to file (saves as ERSI Ascii grid)	
<i>Ldown2d_out</i>	-	0	No grid output
	1	Write grid to file (saves as ERSI Ascii grid)	
<i>Kup2d_out</i>	-	0	No grid output
	1	Write grid to file (saves as ERSI Ascii grid)	
<i>Kdown2d_out</i>	-	0	No grid output

	1	Write grid to file (saves as ERSI Ascii grid)	
<i>GVF_out</i>	-	0	No grid output
		1	Write grid to file (saves as ERSI Ascii grid)
<i>SOLWEIG_Ldown</i>	-	0	Not active (use SUEWS to estimate Ldown above canyon)
		1	Use SOLWEIG to estimate Ldown above canyon
<i>OutInterval</i>	min	Output interval. Set to 60 in current version.	
<i>RunForGrid</i>	-	Grid for which SOLWEIG should be run.	
		-999	All grids (use with care)

Output files

Error messages: problems.txt

If there are problems running the program serious error messages will be written to problems.txt.

- Serious problems will usually cause the program to stop after writing the error message. If this is the case, the last line of problems.txt will contain a non-zero number (the error code).
- If the program runs successfully, problems.txt file ends with

```
Run completed.
0
```

SUEWS has a large number of error messages included to try to capture common errors to help the user determine what the problem is. If you encounter an error that does not provide an error message please capture the details so we can hopefully provide better error messages in future.

See [Troubleshooting](#) section for help solving problems. If the file paths are not correct the program will return an error when run (see [Preparing to run the model](#)).

Error messages: warnings.txt

- If the program encounters a more minor issue it will not stop but a warning may be written to warnings.txt. It is advisable to check the warnings to ensure there is not a more serious problem.
- The warnings.txt file can be large (over several GBs) given warning messages are written out during a large scale simulation, you can use `tail/head` to view the ending/starting part without opening the whole file on Unix-like systems (Linux/mac OS), which may slow down your system.
- To prevent warnings.txt from being written, set **SuppressWarnings** to 1 in [RunControl.nml](#).
- Warning messages are usually written with a grid number, timestamp and error count. If the problem occurs in the initial stages (i.e. before grid numbers and timestamps are assigned, these are printed as 00000).

Summary of model parameters: SS_FileChoices.txt

For each run, the model parameters specified in the input files are written out to the file SS_FileChoices.txt.

Model output files

SSss_YYYY_TT.txt

SUEWS produces the main output file (SSss_YYYY_tt.txt) with time resolution (TT min) set by **ResolutionFilesOut** in [RunControl](#).

Before these main data files are written out, SUEWS provides a summary of the column names, units and variables included in the file Ss_YYYY_TT_OutputFormat.txt (one file per run).

The variables included in the main output file are determined according to **WriteOutOption** set in [RunControl.nml](#).

<i>Column</i>	Name	WriteOutOption	Description
1	Year	0,1,2	Year [YYYY]
2	DOY	0,1,2	Day of year [DOY]
3	Hour	0,1,2	Hour [H]

4	Min	0,1,2	Minute [M]
5	Dectime	0,1,2	Decimal time [-]
6	Kdown	0,1,2	Incoming shortwave radiation [$W m^{-2}$]
7	Kup	0,1,2	Outgoing shortwave radiation [$W m^{-2}$]
8	Ldown	0,1,2	Incoming longwave radiation [$W m^{-2}$]
9	Lup	0,1,2	Outgoing longwave radiation [$W m^{-2}$]
10	Tsurf	0,1,2	Bulk surface temperature [$^{\circ}C$]
11	QN	0,1,2	Net all-wave radiation [$W m^{-2}$]
12	QF	0,1,2	Anthropogenic heat flux [$W m^{-2}$]
13	QS	0,1,2	Storage heat flux [$W m^{-2}$]
14	QH	0,1,2	Sensible heat flux (calculated using SUEWS) [$W m^{-2}$]
15	QE	0,1,2	Latent heat flux (calculated using SUEWS) [$W m^{-2}$]
16	QHlumps	0,1	Sensible heat flux (calculated using LUMPS) [$W m^{-2}$]
17	QElumps	0,1	Latent heat flux (calculated using LUMPS) [$W m^{-2}$]
18	QHresis	0,1	Sensible heat flux (calculated using resistance method) [$W m^{-2}$] Do not use in v2017b!
19	Rain	0,1,2	Rain [mm]
20	Irr	0,1,2	Irrigation [mm]
21	Evap	0,1,2	Evaporation [mm]
22	RO	0,1,2	Runoff [mm]
23	TotCh	0,1,2	Change in surface and soil moisture stores [mm]
24	SurfCh	0,1,2	Change in surface moisture store [mm]
25	State	0,1,2	Surface wetness state [mm]
26	NWtrState	0,1,2	Surface wetness state (for non-water surfaces) [mm]
27	Drainage	0,1,2	Drainage [mm]
28	SMD	0,1,2	Soil moisture deficit [mm]
29	FlowCh	0,1	Additional flow into water body [mm]
30	AddWater	0,1	Additional water flow received from other grids [mm]
31	ROSoil	0,1	Runoff to soil (sub-surface) [mm]
32	ROPipe	0,1	Runoff to pipes [mm]
33	ROImp	0,1	Above ground runoff over impervious surfaces [mm]
34	ROVeg	0,1	Above ground runoff over vegetated surfaces [mm]
35	ROWater	0,1	Runoff for water body [mm]
36	WUInt	0,1	Internal water use [mm]
37	WUEveTr	0,1	Water use for irrigation of evergreen trees [mm]
38	WUDecTr	0,1	Water use for irrigation of deciduous trees [mm]
39	WUGrass	0,1	Water use for irrigation of grass [mm]
40	SMDPaved	0,1	Soil moisture deficit for paved surface [mm]
41	SMDBldgs	0,1	Soil moisture deficit for building surface [mm]
42	SMDEveTr	0,1	Soil moisture deficit for evergreen surface [mm]
43	SMDDecTr	0,1	Soil moisture deficit for deciduous surface [mm]

44	SMDGrass	0,1	Soil moisture deficit for grass surface [mm]
45	SMDBSoil	0,1	Soil moisture deficit for bare soil surface [mm]
46	StPaved	0,1	Surface wetness state for paved surface [mm]
47	StBldgs	0,1	Surface wetness state for building surface [mm]
48	StEveTr	0,1	Surface wetness state for evergreen tree surface [mm]
49	StDecTr	0,1	Surface wetness state for deciduous tree surface [mm]
50	StGrass	0,1	Surface wetness state for grass surface [mm]
51	StBSoil	0,1	Surface wetness state for bare soil surface [mm]
52	StWater	0,1	Surface wetness state for water surface [mm]
53	Zenith	0,1,2	Solar zenith angle [°]
54	Azimuth	0,1,2	Solar azimuth angle [°]
55	AlbBulk	0,1,2	Bulk albedo [-]
56	Fcld	0,1,2	Cloud fraction [-]
57	LAI	0,1,2	Leaf area index [m ² m ⁻²]
58	z0m	0,1	Roughness length for momentum [m]
59	zdm	0,1	Zero-plane displacement height [m]
60	ustar	0,1,2	Friction velocity [m s ⁻¹]
61	Lob	0,1,2	Obukhov length [m]
62	ra	0,1	Aerodynamic resistance [s m ⁻¹]
63	rs	0,1	Surface resistance [s m ⁻¹]
64	Fc	0,1,2	CO ₂ flux [umol m ⁻² s ⁻¹] Do not use in v2017b!
65	FcPhoto	0,1	CO ₂ flux from photosynthesis [umol m ⁻² s ⁻¹] Do not use in v2017b!
66	FcRespi	0,1	CO ₂ flux from respiration [umol m ⁻² s ⁻¹] Do not use in v2017b!
67	FcMetab	0,1	CO ₂ flux from metabolism [umol m ⁻² s ⁻¹] Do not use in v2017b!
68	FcTraff	0,1	CO ₂ flux from traffic [umol m ⁻² s ⁻¹] Do not use in v2017b!
69	FcBuild	0,1	CO ₂ flux from buildings [umol m ⁻² s ⁻¹] Do not use in v2017b!
70	QNSnowFr	1	Net all-wave radiation for snow-free area [W m ⁻²]
71	QNSnow	1	Net all-wave radiation for snow area [W m ⁻²]
72	AlbSnow	1	Snow albedo [-]
73	QM	1	Snow-related heat exchange [W m ⁻²]
74	QMFreeze	1	Internal energy change [W m ⁻²]
75	QMRain	1	Heat released by rain on snow [W m ⁻²]
76	SWE	1	Snow water equivalent [mm]
77	MeltWater	1	Meltwater [mm]
78	MeltWStore	1	Meltwater store [mm]
79	SnowCh	1	Change in snow pack [mm]
80	SnowRPaved	1	Snow removed from paved surface [mm]
81	SnowRBldgs	1	Snow removed from building surface [mm]
82	T2	0,1,2	Air temperature at 2 m agl [°C]
83	Q2	0,1,2	Air specific humidity at 2 m agl [k kg ⁻²]

84	U10	0,1,2	Wind speed at 10 m agl [m s ⁻¹]
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SSss_YYYY_nn_TT.nc (when ncMode=1 in RunControl)

SUEWS can also produce the main output file in netCDF format by setting ncMode=1 (set in RunControl).

As the date and time information is incorporated in the netCDF output as separate dimension, the first five variables in the normal text output file (in .txt) are not included in the netCDF output but other variables are all kept.

N.B., considering the file size limit by the classic netCDF format, the output frequency is determined automatically by the internal SUEWS program setting to avoid the oversize problem in the netCDF files.

SSss_DailyState.txt

Contains information about the state of the surface and soil and vegetation parameters at a time resolution of one day. One file is written for each grid so it may contain multiple years.

Column	Name	Description
1	iy	Year [YYYY]
2	id	Day of year [DOY]
3	HDD1_h	Heating degree days [°C]
4	HDD2_c	Cooling degree days [°C]
5	HDD3_Tmean	Average daily air temperature [°C]
6	HDT4_T5d	5-day running-mean air temperature [°C]
7	P/day	Daily total precipitation [mm]
8	DaysSR	Days since rain [days]
9	GDD1_g	Growing degree days for leaf growth [°C]
10	GDD2_s	Growing degree days for senescence [°C]
11	GDD3_Tmin	Daily minimum temperature [°C]
12	GDD4_Tmax	Daily maximum temperature [°C]
13	GDD5_DayLHrs	Day length [h]
14	LAI_EveTr	Leaf area index of evergreen trees [m ⁻² m ⁻²]
15	LAI_DecTr	Leaf area index of deciduous trees [m ⁻² m ⁻²]
16	LAI_Grass	Leaf area index of grass [m ⁻² m ⁻²]
17	DecidCap	Moisture storage capacity of deciduous trees [mm]
18	Porosity	Porosity of deciduous trees [-]
19	AlbEveTr	Albedo of evergreen trees [-]
20	AlbDecTr	Albedo of deciduous trees [-]
21	AlbGrass	Albedo of grass [-]
22	WU_EveTr(1)	Total water use for evergreen trees [mm]
23	WU_EveTr(2)	Automatic water use for evergreen trees [mm]
24	WU_EveTr(3)	Manual water use for evergreen trees [mm]
25	WU_DecTr(1)	Total water use for deciduous trees [mm]
26	WU_DecTr(2)	Automatic water use for deciduous trees [mm]
27	WU_DecTr(3)	Manual water use for deciduous trees [mm]
28	WU_Grass(1)	Total water use for grass [mm]
29	WU_Grass(2)	Automatic water use for grass [mm]
30	WU_Grass(3)	Manual water use for grass [mm]
31	deltaLAI	Change in leaf area index (normalised 0-1) [-]

32	LAllumps	Leaf area index used in LUMPS (normalised 0-1) [-]
33	AlbSnow	Snow albedo [-]
34	DensSnow_Paved	Snow density - paved surface [kg m ⁻³]
35	DensSnow_Bldgs	Snow density - building surface [kg m ⁻³]
36	DensSnow_EveTr	Snow density - evergreen surface [kg m ⁻³]
37	DensSnow_DecTr	Snow density - deciduous surface [kg m ⁻³]
38	DensSnow_Grass	Snow density - grass surface [kg m ⁻³]
39	DensSnow_BSoil	Snow density - bare soil surface [kg m ⁻³]
40	DensSnow_Water	Snow density - water surface [kg m ⁻³]

InitialConditionsSSss_YYYY.nml

At the end of the model run (or the end of each year in the model run) a new InitialConditions file is written out (to the input folder) for each grid, see [InitialConditionsSSss_YYYY.nml](#)

SSss_YYYY_snow_TT.txt

SUEWS produces a separate output file for snow (when snowUse = 1 in RunControl.nml) with details for each surface type.

File format of SSss_YYYY_snow_60.txt

Column	Name	Description
1	iy	Year [YYYY]
2	id	Day of year [DOY]
3	it	Hour [H]
4	imin	Minute [M]
5	dectime	Decimal time [-]
6	SWE_Paved	Snow water equivalent – paved surface [mm]
7	SWE_Bldgs	Snow water equivalent – building surface [mm]
8	SWE_EveTr	Snow water equivalent – evergreen surface [mm]
9	SWE_DecTr	Snow water equivalent – deciduous surface [mm]
10	SWE_Grass	Snow water equivalent – grass surface [mm]
11	SWE_BSoil	Snow water equivalent – bare soil surface [mm]
12	SWE_Water	Snow water equivalent – water surface [mm]
13	Mw_Paved	Meltwater – paved surface [mm h ⁻¹]
14	Mw_Bldgs	Meltwater – building surface [mm h ⁻¹]
15	Mw_EveTr	Meltwater – evergreen surface [mm h ⁻¹]
16	Mw_DecTr	Meltwater – deciduous surface [mm h ⁻¹]
17	Mw_Grass	Meltwater – grass surface [mm h ⁻¹]
18	Mw_BSoil	Meltwater – bare soil surface [mm h ⁻¹]
19	Mw_Water	Meltwater – water surface [mm h ⁻¹]
20	Qm_Paved	Snowmelt-related heat – paved surface [W m ⁻²]
21	Qm_Bldgs	Snowmelt-related heat – building surface [W m ⁻²]
22	Qm_EveTr	Snowmelt-related heat – evergreen surface [W m ⁻²]
23	Qm_DecTr	Snowmelt-related heat – deciduous surface [W m ⁻²]
24	Qm_Grass	Snowmelt-related heat – grass surface [W m ⁻²]
25	Qm_BSoil	Snowmelt-related heat – bare soil surface [W m ⁻²]
26	Qm_Water	Snowmelt-related heat – water surface [W m ⁻²]
27	Qa_Paved	Advective heat – paved surface [W m ⁻²]
28	Qa_Bldgs	Advective heat – building surface [W m ⁻²]
29	Qa_EveTr	Advective heat – evergreen surface [W m ⁻²]

30	Qa_DecTr	Advective heat – deciduous surface [W m ⁻²]
31	Qa_Grass	Advective heat – grass surface [W m ⁻²]
32	Qa_BSoil	Advective heat – bare soil surface [W m ⁻²]
33	Qa_Water	Advective heat – water surface [W m ⁻²]
34	QmFr_Paved	Heat related to freezing of surface store – paved surface [W m ⁻²]
35	QmFr_Bldgs	Heat related to freezing of surface store – building surface [W m ⁻²]
36	QmFr_EveTr	Heat related to freezing of surface store – evergreen surface [W m ⁻²]
37	QmFr_DecTr	Heat related to freezing of surface store – deciduous surface [W m ⁻²]
38	QmFr_Grass	Heat related to freezing of surface store – grass surface [W m ⁻²]
39	QmFr_BSoil	Heat related to freezing of surface store – bare soil surface [W m ⁻²]
40	QmFr_Water	Heat related to freezing of surface store – water [W m ⁻²]
41	fr_Paved	Fraction of snow – paved surface [-]
42	fr_Bldgs	Fraction of snow – building surface [-]
43	fr_EveTr	Fraction of snow – evergreen surface [-]
44	fr_DecTr	Fraction of snow – deciduous surface [-]
45	fr_Grass	Fraction of snow – grass surface [-]
46	Fr_BSoil	Fraction of snow – bare soil surface [-]
47	RainSn_Paved	Rain on snow – paved surface [mm]
48	RainSn_Bdgs	Rain on snow – building surface [mm]
49	RainSn_EveTr	Rain on snow – evergreen surface [mm]
50	RainSn_DecTr	Rain on snow – deciduous surface [mm]
51	RainSn_Grass	Rain on snow – grass surface [mm]
52	RainSn_BSoil	Rain on snow – bare soil surface [mm]
53	RainSn_Water	Rain on snow – water surface [mm]
54	qn_PavedSnow	Net all-wave radiation – paved surface [W m ⁻²]
55	qn_BldgsSnow	Net all-wave radiation – building surface [W m ⁻²]
56	qn_EveTrSnow	Net all-wave radiation – evergreen surface [W m ⁻²]
57	qn_DecTrSnow	Net all-wave radiation – deciduous surface [W m ⁻²]
58	qn_GrassSnow	Net all-wave radiation – grass surface [W m ⁻²]
59	qn_BSoilSnow	Net all-wave radiation – bare soil surface [W m ⁻²]
60	qn_WaterSnow	Net all-wave radiation – water surface [W m ⁻²]
61	kup_PavedSnow	Reflected shortwave radiation – paved surface [W m ⁻²]
62	kup_BldgsSnow	Reflected shortwave radiation – building surface [W m ⁻²]
63	kup_EveTrSnow	Reflected shortwave radiation – evergreen surface [W m ⁻²]
64	kup_DecTrSnow	Reflected shortwave radiation – deciduous surface [W m ⁻²]
65	kup_GrassSnow	Reflected shortwave radiation – grass surface [W m ⁻²]
66	kup_BSoilSnow	Reflected shortwave radiation – bare soil surface [W m ⁻²]
67	kup_WaterSnow	Reflected shortwave radiation – water surface [W m ⁻²]
68	frMelt_Paved	Amount of freezing melt water – paved surface [mm]
69	frMelt_Bldgs	Amount of freezing melt water – building surface [mm]
70	frMelt_EveTr	Amount of freezing melt water – evergreen surface [mm]
71	frMelt_DecTr	Amount of freezing melt water – deciduous surface [mm]
72	frMelt_Grass	Amount of freezing melt water – grass surface [mm]
73	frMelt_BSoil	Amount of freezing melt water – bare soil surface [mm]
74	frMelt_Water	Amount of freezing melt water – water surface [mm]
75	MwStore_Paved	Melt water store – paved surface [mm]
76	MwStore_Bldgs	Melt water store – building surface [mm]
77	MwStore_EveTt	Melt water store – evergreen surface [mm]
78	MwStore_DecTr	Melt water store – deciduous surface [mm]
79	MwStore_Grass	Melt water store – grass surface [mm]
80	MwStore_BSoil	Melt water store – bare soil surface [mm]
81	MwStore_Water	Melt water store – water surface [mm]
82	DensSnow_Paved	Snow density – paved surface [kg m ⁻³]
83	DensSnow_Bldgs	Snow density – building surface [kg m ⁻³]
84	DensSnow_EveTr	Snow density – evergreen surface [kg m ⁻³]
85	DensSnow_DecTr	Snow density – deciduous surface [kg m ⁻³]
86	DensSnow_Grass	Snow density – grass surface [kg m ⁻³]
87	DensSnow_BSoil	Snow density – bare soil surface [kg m ⁻³]

88	DensSnow_Water	Snow density – water surface [kg m ⁻³]
89	Sd_Paved	Snow depth – paved surface [mm]
90	Sd_Bldgs	Snow depth – building surface [mm]
91	Sd_EveTr	Snow depth – evergreen surface [mm]
92	Sd_DecTr	Snow depth – deciduous surface [mm]
93	Sd_Grass	Snow depth – grass surface [mm]
94	Sd_BSoil	Snow depth – bare soil surface [mm]
95	Sd_Water	Snow depth – water surface [mm]
96	Tsnow_Paved	Snow surface temperature – paved surface [°C]
97	Tsnow_Bldgs	Snow surface temperature – building surface [°C]
98	Tsnow_EveTr	Snow surface temperature – evergreen surface [°C]
99	Tsnow_DecTr	Snow surface temperature – deciduous surface [°C]
100	Tsnow_Grass	Snow surface temperature – grass surface [°C]
101	Tsnow_BSoil	Snow surface temperature – bare soil surface [°C]
102	Tsnow_Water	Snow surface temperature – water surface [°C]

SSss_YYYY_BL.txt

Meteorological variables modelled by CBL portion of the model are output in to this file created for each day with time step (see section CBL Input).

Col	Header	Name	Units
1	iy	Year [YYYY]	
2	id	Day of year [DoY]	
3	it	Hour [H]	
4	imin	Minute [M]	
5	dectime	Decimal time [-]	
6	zi	Convective boundary layer height	m
7	Theta	Potential temperature in the inertial sublayer	K
8	Q	Specific humidity in the inertial sublayer	g kg ⁻¹
9	theta+	Potential temperature just above the CBL	K
10	q+	Specific humidity just above the CBL	g kg ⁻¹
11	Temp_C	Air temperature	°C
12	RH	Relative humidity	%
13	QH_use	Sensible heat flux used for calculation	W m ⁻²
14	QE_use	Latent heat flux used for calculation	W m ⁻²
15	Press_hPa	Pressure used for calculation	hPa
16	avul	Wind speed used for calculation	m s ⁻¹
17	ustar	Friction velocity used for calculation	m s ⁻¹
18	avdens	Air density used for calculation	kg m ⁻³
19	lv_J_kg	Latent heat of vaporization used for calculation	J kg ⁻¹
20	avcp	Specific heat capacity used for calculation	J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
21	gamt	Vertical gradient of potential temperature	K m ⁻¹
22	gamq	Vertical gradient of specific humidity	kg kg ⁻¹ m ⁻¹

SOLWEIGpoiOut.txt

Calculated variables from POI, point of interest (row, col) stated in SOLWEIGinput.nml.

SOLWEIG model output file format: SOLWEIGpoiOUT.txt

Col	Header	Name	Units
1	id	Day of year	
2	dectime	Decimal time	
3	azimuth	Azimuth angle of the Sun	°
4	altitude	Altitude angle of the Sun	°

5	GlobalRad	Input Kdn	W m ⁻²
6	DiffuseRad	Diffuse shortwave radiation	W m ⁻²
7	DirectRad	Direct shortwave radiation	W m ⁻²
8	Kdown2d	Incoming shortwave radiation at POI	W m ⁻²
9	Kup2d	Outgoing shortwave radiation at POI	W m ⁻²
10	Ksouth	Shortwave radiation from south at POI	W m ⁻²
11	Kwest	Shortwave radiation from west at POI	W m ⁻²
12	Knorth	Shortwave radiation from north at POI	W m ⁻²
13	Keast	Shortwave radiation from east at POI	W m ⁻²
14	Ldown2d	Incoming longwave radiation at POI	W m ⁻²
15	Lup2d	Outgoing longwave radiation at POI	W m ⁻²
16	Lsouth	Longwave radiation from south at POI	W m ⁻²
17	Lwest	Longwave radiation from west at POI	W m ⁻²
18	Lnorth	Longwave radiation from north at POI	W m ⁻²
19	Least	Longwave radiation from east at POI	W m ⁻²
20	Tmrt	Mean Radiant Temperature	°C
21	I0	theoretical value of maximum incoming solar radiation	W m ⁻²
22	CI	clearness index for Ldown (Lindberg et al. 2008)	
23	gvf	Ground view factor (Lindberg and Grimmond 2011)	
24	shadow	Shadow value (0= shadow, 1 = sun)	
25	svf	Sky View Factor from ground and buildings	
26	svfbuveg	Sky View Factor from ground, buildings and vegetation	
27	Ta	Air temperature	°C
28	Tg	Surface temperature	°C

SSss_YYYY_ESTM_TT.txt

If the ESTM model option is run, the following output file is created. ESTM output file format

Col	Header	Name	Units
1	iy	Year	
2	id	Day of year	
3	it	Hour	
4	imin	Minute	
5	dectime	Decimal time	
6	QSnet	Net storage heat flux (QSwall+QSground+QS)	W m ⁻²
7	QSair	Storage heat flux into air	W m ⁻²
8	QSwall	Storage heat flux into wall	W m ⁻²
9	QSroof	Storage heat flux into roof	W m ⁻²
10	QSground	Storage heat flux into ground	W m ⁻²
11	QSibld	Storage heat flux into internal elements in building	W m ⁻²
12	Twall1	Temperature in the first layer of wall (outer-most)	K
13	Twall2	Temperature in the first layer of wall	K
14	Twall3	Temperature in the first layer of wall	K
15	Twall4	Temperature in the first layer of wall	K
16	Twall5	Temperature in the first layer of wall (inner-most)	K
17	Troof1	Temperature in the first layer of roof (outer-most)	K
18	Troof2	Temperature in the first layer of roof	K
19	Troof3	Temperature in the first layer of roof	K
20	Troof4	Temperature in the first layer of roof	K
21	Troof5	Temperature in the first layer of ground (inner-most)	K
22	Tground1	Temperature in the first layer of ground (outer-most)	K
23	Tground2	Temperature in the first layer of ground	K
24	Tground3	Temperature in the first layer of ground	K
25	Tground4	Temperature in the first layer of ground	K
26	Tground5	Temperature in the first layer of ground (inner-most)	K
27	Tibld1	Temperature in the first layer of internal elements	K

28	Tibld2	Temperature in the first layer of internal elements	K
29	Tibld3	Temperature in the first layer of internal elements	K
30	Tibld4	Temperature in the first layer of internal elements	K
31	Tibld5	Temperature in the first layer of internal elements	K
32	Tabld	Air temperature in buildings	K

Troubleshooting

How to create a directory?

please search the web using this phrase if you do not know how to create a folder or directory

How to unzip a file

please search the web using this phrase if you do not know how to unzip a file

A text editor

is a program to edit plain text files. If you search on the web using the phrase ‘text editor’ you will find numerous programs. These include for example, NotePad, EditPad, Text Pad etc

Command prompt

From Start select run –type cmd – this will open a window. Change directory to the location of where you stored your files. The following website may be helpful if you do not know what a command prompt is: <http://dosprompt.info/>

Day of year [DOY]

January 1st is day 1, February 1st is day 32. If you search on the web using the phrase ‘day of year calendar’ you will find tables that allow rapid conversions. Remember that after February 28th DOY will be different between leap years and non-leap years.

First things to Check if the program seems to have problems

- Check the problems.txt file.
- Check file options – in RunControl.nml.
- Look in the output directory for the SS_FileChoices.txt. This allows you to check all options that were used in the run. You may want to compare it with the original version supplied with the model.
- Note there can not be missing time steps in the data. If you need help with this you may want to checkout [UMEP](#)

A pop-up saying “file path not found”

This means the program cannot find the file paths defined in RunControl.nml file. Possible solutions:

- Check that you have created the folder that you specified in RunControl.nml.
- Check does the output directory exist?
- Check that you have a single or double quotes around the FileInputPath, FileOutputPath and FileCode

“%sat_vap_press.f temp=0.0000 pressure dectime”

Temperature is zero in the calculation of water vapour pressure parameterization.

- You don't need to worry if the temperature should be (is) 0°C.
- If it should not be 0°C this suggests that there is a problem with the data.

%T changed to fit limits

- [TL =0.1]/ [TL =39.9] You may want to change the coefficients for surface resistance. If you have data from these temperatures, we would happily determine them.

%Iteration loop stopped for too stable conditions.

- [zL]/[USTAR] This warning indicates that the atmospheric stability gets above 2. In these conditions MO theory is not necessarily valid. The iteration loop to calculate the Obukhov length and friction velocity is stopped so that stability does not get too high values. This is something you do not need to worry as it does not mean wrong input data.

“Reference to undefined variable, array element or function result”

- Parameter(s) missing from input files.

See also the error messages provided in problems.txt and warnings.txt

Email list

- SUEWS email list

<https://www.lists.reading.ac.uk/mailman/listinfo/met-suews>

- UMEP email list

<https://www.lists.reading.ac.uk/mailman/listinfo/met-umep>

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Notation

	Definition
λF	frontal area index
ΔQ_S	storage heat flux
<i>BLUEWS</i>	Boundary Layer part of SUEWS
	<p>Relation between BLUEWS and SUEWS Source: ^[17]</p>
<i>Bldgs</i>	Building surface
<i>CBL</i>	Convective boundary layer
<i>DEM</i>	Digital Elevation Model
<i>DSM</i>	Digital surface model
<i>DTM</i>	Digital Terrain Model
<i>DecTr</i>	deciduous trees and shrubs
<i>EveTr</i>	Evergreen trees and shrubs
<i>ESTM</i>	Element Surface Temperature Method (Offerle et al., 2005 ^[13])
<i>Grass</i>	Grass surface
<i>BSoil</i>	Unmanaged land and/or bare soil
$L\downarrow$	incoming longwave radiation
<i>LAI</i>	Leaf area index
<i>LUMPS</i>	Local scale Urban Meteorological Parameterization Scheme (Loridan et al. 2011 ^[5])
<i>NARP</i>	Net All-wave Radiation Parameterization (Offerle et al. 2003 ^[4] , Loridan et al. 2011 ^[5])
<i>OHM</i>	Objective Hysteresis Model (Grimmond et al. 1991 ^[9] , Grimmond & Oke 1999a ^[10] , 2002 ^[11])
<i>Paved</i>	Paved surface
Q^*	net all-wave radiation
Q_E	latent heat flux
Q_F	anthropogenic heat flux
Q_H	sensible heat flux
<i>SOLWEIG</i>	The solar and longwave environmental irradiance geometry model (Lindberg et al. 2008 ^[18] , Lindberg and Grimmond 2011 ^[19])
<i>SVF</i>	Sky view factor
<i>theta</i>	potential temperature
<i>tt</i>	time step of data
<i>UMEP</i>	<u>Urban Multi-scale Environmental Predictor</u>
<i>Water</i>	Water surface
z_i	Convective boundary layer height

Development, Suggestions and Support

1. Coding Guidelines
2. Recommendations, Errors, Help/Updates - please join our email list
 1. www.lists.reading.ac.uk/mailman/listinfo/met-suews
 2. As UMEP has a number of tools to support SUEWS you may want to join that list also www.lists.reading.ac.uk/mailman/listinfo/met-umep

Version History

New in SUEWS Version 2017b (released 1 August 2017)

1. Surface-level diagnostics: T2 (air temperature at 2 m agl), Q2 (air specific humidity at 2 m agl) and U10 (wind speed at 10 m agl) added as default output.
2. Output in netCDF format. Please note this feature is **NOT** enabled in the public release due to the dependency of netCDF library. Assistance in enabling this feature may be requested to the development team via [SUEWS mail list](#).
3. Edits to the manual.
4. New capabilities being developed, including two new options for calculating storage heat flux (AnOHM, ESTM) and modelling of carbon dioxide fluxes. These are currently under development and **should not be used** in v2017b.
5. Known issues
 1. BLUEWS parameters need to be checked
 2. Observed soil moisture can not be used as an input
 3. Wind direction is not currently downscaled so non -999 values will cause an error.

New in SUEWS Version 2017a (Feb 2017)

1. Changes to input file formats (including RunControl.nml and InitialConditions files) to facilitate setting up and running the model. Met forcing files no longer need two rows of -9 at the end to indicate the end of the file.
2. Changes to output file formats (now option to write out only a subset of variables, rather than all variables).
3. SUEWS can now disaggregate forcing files to the model time-step and aggregate output at the model time-step to lower resolution. This removes the need for the python wrapper used with previous versions.
4. InitialConditions format and requirements changed. A single file can now be provided for multiple grids. SUEWS will approximate most (but not all) of the required initial conditions if values are unknown. (However, if detailed information about the initial conditions is known, this can still be provided to and used by SUEWS.)
5. Leaf area index calculations now use parameters provided for each vegetated surface (previously only the deciduous tree LAI development parameters were applied to all vegetated surfaces).
6. For compatibility with GIS, **the sign convention for longitude has been changed**. Now negative values are to the west, positive values are to the east. Note this appears to have been incorrectly coded in previous versions (but may not necessarily have been problematic).
7. Storage heat flux calculation adapted for shorter (sub-hourly) model time-step: hysteresis calculation now based on running means over the previous hour.
8. Improved error handling, including separate files for serious errors (problems.txt) and less critical issues (warnings.txt).
9. Edits to the manual.
10. New capabilities being developed, including two new options for calculating storage heat flux (AnOHM, ESTM) and modelling of carbon dioxide fluxes. These are currently under development and **should not be used** in v2017a.

New in SUEWS Version 2016a (released 21 June 2016)

PDF Manual for v2016a

1. Major changes to the input file formats to facilitate the running of multiple grids and multiple years. Surface characteristics are provided in SiteSelect.txt and other input files are cross-referenced via codes or profile types.
2. The surface types have been altered:
 - Previously, grass surfaces were entered separately as irrigated grass and unirrigated grass surfaces, whilst the 'unmanaged' land cover fraction was assumed by the model to behave as

- unirrigated grass. There is now a single surface type for grass (total for irrigated plus unirrigated) and a new bare soil surface type.
- The proportion of irrigated vegetation must now be specified for grass, evergreen trees and deciduous trees individually.
3. The entire model now runs at a time step specified by the user. Note that 5 min is strongly recommended. (Previously only the water balance calculations were done at 5 min with the energy balance calculations at 60 min).
 4. Surface conductance now depends on the soil moisture under the vegetated surfaces only (rather than the total soil moisture for the whole study area as previously).
 5. Albedo of evergreen trees and grass surfaces can now change with leaf area index as was previously possible for deciduous trees only.
 6. New suggestions in Troubleshooting section.
 7. Edits to the manual.
 8. CBL model included.
 9. SUEWS has been incorporated into UMEP

New in SUEWS Version 2014b (released 8 October 2014)

[V2014 manual] These affect the run configuration if previously run with older versions of the model:

1. New input of three additional columns in the Meteorological input file (diffusive and direct solar radiation, and wind direction)
2. Change of input variables in InitialConditions.nml file. Note we now refer to CT as ET (ie. Evergreen trees rather than coniferous trees)
3. In GridConnectionsYYYY.txt, the site names should now be without the underscore (e.g “Sm” and not “Sm_”)

Other issues:

1. Number of grid areas that can be modelled (for one grid, one year 120; for one grid two years 80)
2. Comment about Time interval of input data
3. Bug fix: Column headers corrected in 5 min file
4. Bug fix: Surface state 60 min file - corrected to give the last 5 min of the hour (rather than cumulating through the hour)
5. Bug fix: units in the Horizontal soil water transfer
6. ErrorHints: More have been added to the problems.txt file.
7. Manual: new section on running the model appropriately
8. Manual: notation table updated
9. Possibility to add snow accumulation and melt: new paper

Järvi L, Grimmond CSB, Taka M, Nordbo A, Setälä H, and Strachan IB 2014: Development of the Surface Urban Energy and Water balance Scheme (SUEWS) for cold climate cities, *Geosci. Model Dev.* 7, 1691-1711, doi:10.5194/gmd-7-1691-2014.

New in SUEWS Version 2014a.1 (released 26 February 2014)

1. Please see the large number of changes made in the 2014a release.
2. This is a minor change to address installing the software.
3. Minor updates to the manual

New in SUEWS Version 2014a (released 21 February 2014)

1. Bug fix: External irrigation is calculated as combined from automatic and manual irrigation and during precipitation events the manual irrigation is reduced to 60% of the calculated values. In previous version of the model, the irrigation was in all cases taken 60% of the calculated value, but now this has been fixed.

2. In previous versions of the model, irrigation was only allowed on the irrigated grass surface type. Now, irrigation is also allowed on evergreen and deciduous trees/shrubs surfaces. These are not however treated as separate surfaces, but the amount of irrigation is evenly distributed to the whole surface type in the modelled area. The amount of water is calculated using same equation as for grass surface (equation 5 in Järvi et al. 2011), and the fraction of irrigated trees/shrubs (relative to the area of tree/shrubs surface) is set in the gis file (See Table 4.11: SSss_YYYY.gis)
3. In the current version of the model, the user is able to adjust the leaf-on and leaf-off lengths in the FunctionalTypes.nml file. In addition, user can choose whether to use temperature dependent functions or combination of temperature and day length (advised to be used at high-latitudes)
4. In the gis-file, there is a new variable Alt that is the area altitude above sea level. If not known exactly use an approximate value.
5. Snow removal profile has been added to the HourlyProfileSSss_YYYY.txt. Not yet used!
6. Model time interval has been changed from minutes to seconds. Preferred interval is 3600 seconds (1 hour)
7. Manual correction: input variable Soil moisture said soil moisture deficit in the manual – word removed
8. Multiple compiled versions of SUEWS released. There are now users in Apple, Linux and Windows environments. So we will now release compiled versions for more operating systems (section 3).
9. There are some changes in the output file columns so please, check the respective table of each used output file.
10. Bug fix: with very small amount of vegetation in an area – impacted Phenology for LUMPS

New in SUEWS Version 2013a

1. Radiation selection bug fixed
2. Aerodynamic resistance – when very low - no longer reverts to neutral (which caused a large jump) – but stays low
3. Irrigation day of week fixed
4. New error messages
5. min file – now includes a decimal time column – see Section 5.4 – Table 5.3

New in SUEWS Version 2012b

1. Error message generated if all the data are not available for the surface resistance calculations
2. Error message generated if wind data are below zero plane displacement height.
3. All error messages now written to ‘Problem.txt’ rather than embedded in an ErrorFile. Note some errors will be written and the program will continue others will stop the program.
4. Default variables removed (see below). Model will stop if any data are problematic. File should be checked to ensure that reasonable data are being used. If an error occurs when there should not be one let us know as it may mean we have made the limits too restrictive.

Contents no longer used File defaultFcld=0.1 defaultPres=1013 defaultRH=50 defaultT=10 defaultU=3

RunControl.nml

- Just delete lines from file
- Values you had were likely different from these example value shown here

New in SUEWS Version 2012a

1. Improved error messages when an error is encountered. Error message will generally be written to the screen and to the file ‘problems.txt’
2. Format of all input files have changed.
3. New excel spreadsheet and R programme to help prepare required data files. (Not required)
4. Format of coef flux (OHM) input files have changed.
 - This allows for clearer identification for users of the coefficients that are actually to be used

- This requires an additional file with coefficients. These do not need to be adjusted but new coefficients can be added. We would appreciate receiving additional coefficients so they can be included in future releases – Please email Sue.
- 5. Storage heat flux (OHM) coefficients can be changed by
 - time of year (summer, winter)
 - surface wetness state
- 6. New files are written: DailyState.txt
 - Provides the status of variables that are updated on a daily or basis or a snapshot at the end of each day.
- 7. Surface Types
 - Clarification of surface types has been made. See GIS and OHM related files

New in SUEWS Version2011b

1. Storage heat flux (ΔQ_s) and anthropogenic heat flux (QF) can be set to be 0 W m^{-2}
2. Calculation of hydraulic conductivity in soil has been improved and HydraulicConduct in SUEWSInput.nml is replaced with name SatHydraulicConduct
3. Following removed from HeaderInput.nml
 - HydraulicConduct
 - GrassFractionIrrigated
 - PavedFractionIrrigated
 - TreeFractionIrrigated

The lower three are now determined from the water use behaviour used in SUEWS

1. Following added to HeaderInput.nml
 - SatHydraulicConduct
 - defaultQf
 - defaultQs
2. If ΔQ_s and QF are not calculated in the model but are given as an input, the missing data is replaced with the default values.
3. Added to SAHP input file
 - AHDIUPRF – diurnal profile used if AnthropHeatChoice = 1

V2012a this became obsolete OHM file (SSss_YYYY.ohm)

Differences between SUEWS, LUMPS and FRAISE

The largest difference between LUMPS and SUEWS is that the latter simulates the urban water balance in detail while LUMPS takes a simpler approach for the sensible and latent heat fluxes and the water balance (“water bucket”). The calculation of evaporation/latent heat in SUEWS is more biophysically based. Due to its simplicity, LUMPS requires less parameters in order to run. SUEWS gives turbulent heat fluxes calculated with both models as an output. **The model can run LUMPS alone without running SUEWS (Table 4.1 – SUEWSStatus).**

Similarities and differences between LUMPS and SUEWS.

	LUMPS	SUEWS
<i>Net all-wave radiation (Q^*)</i>	Input or NARP	Input or NARP
<i>Storage heat flux (ΔQ_s)</i>	Input or from OHM	Input or from OHM
<i>Anthropogenic heat flux (QF)</i>	Input or calculated	Input or calculated

<i>Latent heat (QE)</i>	DeBruin and Holtslag (1982)	Penman-Monteith equation2
<i>Sensible heat flux (QH)</i>	DeBruin and Holtslag (1982)	Residual from available energy minus QE
<i>Water balance</i>	No water balance included	Running water balance of canopy and water balance of soil
<i>Soil moisture</i>	Not considered	Modelled
<i>Surface wetness</i>	Simple water bucket model	Running water balance
<i>Irrigation</i>	Only fraction of surface area that is irrigated	Input or calculated with a simple model
<i>Surface cover</i>	buildings, paved, vegetation	buildings, paved, coniferous and deciduous trees/shrubs, irrigated and unirrigated grass

FRAISE Flux Ratio – Active Index Surface Exchange

FRAISE provides an estimate of mean midday (± 3 h around solar noon) energy partitioning from information on the surface characteristics and estimates of the mean midday incoming radiative energy and anthropogenic heat release. Please refer to Loridan and Grimmond (2012)^[42] for further details.

<i>Topic</i>	FRAISE	LUMPS	SUEWS
Complexity	Simplest: FRAISE		More complex: SUEWS
Software provided:	R code	Windows exe (written in Fortran)	Windows exe (written in Fortran) - other versions available
Applicable period:	Midday (within 3 h of solar noon)	hourly	5 min-hourly-annual
Unique features:	calculates active surface – and fluxes	radiation and energy balances	radiation, energy and water balance (includes LUMPS)

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